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Baseline study and sample database for conditions of employment and unemployment

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<p>Abstract</p> <p>Objectives: The aim of this study is to explore the factors which lead to a job for unemployed persons. We used a holistic model based on person-organisation fit and person-job fit. Central elements here are barriers and facilitators to distinguish the unemployed who found a job and the unemployed who remained unemployed</p> <p>Methods: A follow-up study sample of 1342 persons. The online survey took place between spring 2022 and winter 2023. The face-to-face interviews were conducted in spring 2023.</p> <p>Results: 59.6% of the formerly unemployed found a job. Unemployed people who found a job had a higher level of career adaptability as a facilitator, better health, and less loneliness as a barrier than those who remained unemployed.</p> <p>Conclusions: We proofed our model and demonstrated it to be a good predictor for employment.</p> <p>Keywords: Person-Job-Fit (P-J-Fit); Person-Organisation-Fit (P-O-Fit); long-term unemployment, employment.</p>	
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Executive summary

Important findings

- Career adaptability control and self-regulation goal are significant predictors differentiating unemployed people who found a job and who stayed unemployed.
- High career adaptability, a good health, a low level of loneliness as well as anxiety and procrastination are helpful for finding a job.
- Being younger, having a better education, being of Swiss nationality and of female gender increases the chance of getting a job.
- None of the job-related variables such as P-O-Fit, P-J-Fit, job passion and job commitment could significantly predict the chances of finding employment.

Overview of tested hypotheses

Hypothesis	State
Hypothesis 1: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 have higher scores in facilitators at t1 than unemployed people who remained unemployed.	Marginally confirmed
Hypothesis 2: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 have lower scores in barriers at t1 than unemployed people who remained unemployed.	Partially confirmed
Hypothesis 3: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 are different in sociodemographic factors at t1 compared to unemployed people who remained unemployed.	Confirmed
Hypotheses 4: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 have higher scores in job-related variables at t1 than unemployed people who remained unemployed.	Rejected
Hypothesis 5: Unemployed people who have found a job at t2 had more facilitators and less barriers at t1 than unemployed people who remained unemployed.	Partially confirmed
Hypothesis 6: People who are employed both at t1 and t2 differ in facilitators and barriers at t2 compared to former unemployed who found a job by t2.	Not confirmed

In this document, the designation **t1** is used for survey wave 1 and **t2** for survey wave 2 (please refer to chapter 3.2 Sample).

1 Introduction

In our highly complex and digitalised society, job matching is a challenge. It is challenging to find the right person for the right job to achieve optimal performance that produces the best possible results for the employer, the employees, the economy, and society. Matching methods and elaborate assessments are used for this purpose, but with debatable success. A major shortcoming is that not all factors that play a role in the fit are considered, while for other factors, their predictive power for professional success has not been proven. There are also two factors to consider: the person must fit into the company culture and at the same time, be the right person for the specific job. In general, there are no sufficient scientific studies that prove the effectiveness of job matching. This project remedies this by comparing unemployed and employed people in a longitudinal study, to ascertain the factors that promise success by enabling the employed to retain their job and for the unemployed to successfully find a job.

Being jobless is a single event, compared to unemployment, which is understood as a state. Involuntary job separation occurs when employees are made redundant for many reasons such as performance issues, interpersonal conflicts, health reasons, job displacement, etc. Voluntary job separation occurs due to different inconsistencies like lack of socioeconomic mobility, motivation, politics, communication conflicts, etc.

The model of Kristof (1996, 2005) was selected for this study, as it represents a conceptualisation of the Person-Organisation Fit (P-O-Fit); including the complementary and supplementary fit. Complementary fit takes place when a person's or an organization's characteristics offer what the other wants and therefore one of the two entities fits into the other. Needs- supplies (NS) happens when the organization supplies what the individual needs and demand-abilities (DA) fit occurs when the individual has the knowledge, skills, and abilities the organization demands of them. Supplementary fit occurs when a person and an organisation have similar or matching characteristics such as values, goals, personality, culture.

In her model she considers different types of fit: P-O-Fit means the congruence between organisational and individual values as well as the match between individual needs and preferences and organisational systems and structures; Person-Job-Fit (P-J-Fit) addresses employees who use their competencies adequately and address their professional demands. Person-Superior Fit (P-S-Fit) is a congruence in value, personality and goal between the supervisor and subordinate (Kristoff-Brown et al., 2005).

A good P-O fit can lead to the sustainable job, when employees have the competencies, knowledge and skills, commitment and motivation, and their needs are satisfied (wages, recognition, time, etc.); there is no need to change the job ("turnover intention"). It must be right on both sides and the values must be the same for the employer and employee (Chernyshenko et al., 2009).

Job seekers prefer organisations where their characteristics match the organisational characteristics (Cable & Judge, 1994; Judge & Bretz, 1992). In the same context, companies need to find the best fit for the job and organisation; otherwise, they run the risk of having to bear the high costs of misfits, when they have to face employee turnover, and deal with

all the resulting direct (cost of selection and training of new employees, etc.) and indirect cost (loss of knowledge, decrease of productivity, etc.) (Holtom et al., 2008).

This survey aims to ascertain the factors that contribute to an adequate and sustainable P-O-fit. We desire to contribute to a better understanding and consideration of a “suitable mix” of variables that facilitates a sustainable Organization-Person fit, viz., “Facilitators” such as career adaptability, self-esteem, self-regulation and networks, “Barriers” and “Ambiguities” like unemployment history, depression, health, burnout, procrastination, and dark triad.

We describe the factors crucial for sustainable fits, focussing thereafter on empirical studies that support the importance of the included factors; and finally, we describe our research proposal.

The Hecat project started simultaneously with the outbreak of the pandemic in Europe. Covid-19 has caused global unemployment and precarious employment has emerged. Europe has also been hit by this crisis; therefore, Hecat's responsibility has grown. In Switzerland, the restrictive measures were not as strict as in other European countries, which meant that the economic losses were not as great as in other European countries. Policymakers took various measures to protect jobs in order to limit collateral damage and thus have to lay off employees. Unemployment figures nevertheless rose to a high of 3.7%. In 2020, unemployment rose by an annual average of 0.8% compared to 2019.

We are pleased to contribute our practical experience in the placement, networking and up-skilling of unemployed people and a political action, in the Hecat project as a non-EU country. In our 17 years of professional experience in supporting unemployed people in their job search, the NGO "Platform Networking for Jobs" has gained experience and expertise in strengthening the self-confidence of unemployed people through trainings and workshops, augmenting, and reinforcing their skills, self-awareness and self-control, to be successful in their job search. We also link jobseekers with decision-makers with a success average rate of 70%.

This paper is organised as follows. First, in chapter 0, we summarise our theoretical frame as well as our own extension thereof. The P-O-Fit is measured here through different variables such as the “Facilitators”, “Barriers” and “Ambiguities”. The following section 3 concerns the methodology implemented. Section 4 provides detailed documentation of the data and outcomes; section 0 reports the limitations of the study and Section 0 the conclusions.

2 Theoretical Frame

2.1 Model

Kristof's (1996) model is relevant and the basis of this study, and presents a conceptualisation that distinguishes between complementary and complementary fit. Kristof-Brown et al., (2005) demonstrated the concepts of the theory in a meta-analysis of empirical studies.

Figure 1 - Extended Model based on Kristof 1996, 2005

Person-Organisation fit is defined as the compatibility between people and the organisation in which they work (Kristof, 1996, 2005). In Kristof's model, supplementary fit is represented as the relationship between the fundamental characteristics of an organisation and a person. For the organisation, these characteristics traditionally include culture, values, norms, goals, financial situation, etc. On the individual's side, the characteristics are values, goals, personality, and attitudes. When there is a similarity between an organization and a person in these characteristics, supplementary fit is said to exist (Kristof, 1996).

In addition to these basic characteristics, organisations and people could also be described by what they supply and demand in employment agreements. These demands and supplies are likely to be influenced by the underlying characteristics of the two entities; however, they represent distinct dimensions on which fit or misfit may occur (Kristof, 1996). More specifically, organisations supply financial, physical, and psychological resources as well as the task-related, interpersonal, and growth opportunities that are demanded by employees. When these organisational supplies meet employees' demands, the needs-supplies fit is achieved. Similarly, organisations demand contributions from their employees in terms of time, effort, commitment, knowledge, skills, and abilities. Demands-abilities fit are achieved when the employee's supplies meet organisational demands. Kristoff-Brown et al., (2005, 288) conceptualizes fit further: complementary fit occurs when individuals' characteristics

fill a gap in the current environment, or vice versa. The second major conceptualization of fit, supplementary fit, exists when the individual and the environment are similar.

2.1.1 Various facets of the fit

Over the years, the P-O-Fit model has been further developed and elaborated. An overview of the discussion is presented in the following.

The fit of individuals varies over time and can evolve into different experiential profiles. It is hence too narrow to be categorised in a dichotomous dimension of fit/unfit (Kristof-Brown 2000). Besides, it is crucial to distinguish between high fit and low fit (Vleughels et al., 2019), as well as to consider person-job fit, person-supervisor fit, person-group fit (co-workers fit), and person-organisation fit over time.

Job seekers' perceptions of the organisation's values and their own values are associated positively with their perceived fit with the organisation that leads to decisions about their job choice (Cable & Judge, 1996). Aligned to these findings, "The measure of employees' and supervisors' fit perceptions is a more reliable predictor of individual results" (Cable & Judge, 1996; Edwards, Caplan, & Harrison, 1998).

Trust and effective communication between individuals and organisations are crucial for achieving a considerable P-O fit. This requires common values (Edwards & Cable, 2009). Evaluations of employee performance are at the highest when supervisors, employees, and the organisation share similar organisational values and goals to be achieved. Kristof-Brown (2005) validated these results through a meta-analysis, where P-S fit had a stronger relationship with job satisfaction and performance.

Therefore, performance evaluations are suggested to be positive when the P-O fit of the supervisor is also high (Hamstra et al., 2019, Gregory et al., 2010; Vilela, González, & Ferrín, 2008). Hence low fitting supervisors may reduce the performance and commitment of their employees with high P-O fit (Preenen, Van Vianen, & De Pater, 2014).

In P-O-Fit, there is a need to identify theory-based moderators responsible for conditioning antecedent-fit and fit-consequence relationships. As Hamstra et al., (2019) reported, employees' perceived P-O fit was positively associated with their performance evaluation when the supervisor's perceived P-O fit was high, whereas this association was absent when the supervisor's perceived P-O fit was low. Therefore, the role of the immediate supervisor is central to the performance evaluation of employees.

According to Gallup¹, more than half the employees (51%) say they are actively looking for a new job or watching for openings: the survey findings of Mental Health America (2017) showed that 71 percent of the respondents were thinking about, or actively looking for new job opportunities. Considerable discrepancies have been analysed between the employed and non-employed when accessing job offers. Employed people are efficient in their search effort because they get more offers and higher outcomes with less effort. Differences are

¹ www.gallup.com

also consistent when accessing networks that facilitate qualitatively better job offers for the employed than for the unemployed (Faberman et al., 2017, 2019). Nevertheless, stigma and discrimination towards the unemployed are consistent (Krug et al., 2019; Omori, 1997). Our focus of interest is to tackle sustainable work. Our attention is therefore based on the relevant aspects of the following model, “From the needs-supplies perspective, P-O fit occurs when an organisation satisfies an individual’s needs, desires, or preferences. In contrast, the demands-abilities perspective suggests that fit occurs when an individual has the abilities required to meet organizational demands” (Kristof, 1996 p.3).

P-O fit is defined as the compatibility between people and organisations that occurs when (a) at least one entity provides what the other needs or (b) they share similar fundamental characteristics, or (c) both. Kristof presents evidence that P-O-Fit is important in job search, job choice, recruitment, selection, and intention to quit. If career adaptability is strong and it is actively ensured that the skills and competencies of the labour market meet its requirements, then job opportunities are optimised. Due to these measures, the possibility of getting an employment opportunity increases (Duarte et al., 2017; Pulakos et al., 2000).

A higher P-O Fit should bring satisfaction to the individuals and diminish the intention to quit (Tang et al, 2021). However, this is not always the case; conversely, many authors (B. Schneider, 1987; B. Schneider, Kristof, Goldstein, & Smith, 1995; B. Schneider, Smith, & Goldstein, 1994; Walsh, 1987) found that high levels of homogeneity of P-O fit produce negative outcomes for the organisations. This circumstance could be related to employees’ willingness to continue to work on their career and to create bigger challenges than the previous one, till they no longer feel challenged.

As indicated, the Fit can change over time; it could be a false assumption during the job interview for both sides, the organisation or the employee not acting according to the agreed policy, such as gender leadership promotion which does not happen.

The working process is highly dynamic, less predictable and the career progression is nonlinear (Savickas et al., 2009). Employees’ and employers’ satisfaction with the Fit facilitates a long-term working relationship. Hence, organizations are interested in long-term and loyal contract relations, and demand from workers suitable qualifications, skills, and competencies. The most valuable capital of the organisation is its employees. Therefore, employers want to retain their performing workers, offering them all kinds of incentives, thus securing a long-term loyalty to the organisation. Likewise, workers supply their labour and skills and expect satisfying jobs and remuneration, *inter alia*. In this sense, employees negotiate a return on previous investments, which is aligned to the Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1993; Mincer, 1974). Employees who have the demanded experience, skills, competencies and are adaptable enjoy more work stability (De Cuyper et al., 2012). For some job seekers, changing jobs is associated with a lot of stress and frustration (Chadi & Hetschko, 2015) and for employers, the costs associated with a change of workforce are high (Muehlemann & Leiser, 2018).

2.1.2 Transition to the model of this study

We assume that a fit theory best represents what is relevant in job search and sustainable work. The job seeker has to fit the job on offer, in terms of a number of criteria. To do this,

we chose Kristof's model as a starting point and developed it further, since Kristof does not consider the macroeconomic level, nor does it differentiate the personal level. There are factors that are clearly in favour of a fit, like self-regulation, or clearly against it, like depression. The Big Five and Dark Triad personality factors can have quite different effects. In addition, there are factors that Kristof did not take into account, such as career adaptability or self-regulation, but which are important for the P-O-Fit.

Kristof's model is the basis for our model, where we retain supplies and demands, but additionally, differentiate between personal characteristics such as facilitators, barriers, and ambiguous factors. Further, we have also added features on the organisation side, such as the financial and economic situation and the economic system. The difference is that on both sides, barriers have a negative effect on the fit, e.g., if an employer is in a difficult financial situation, this could be negative for sustainability. If an employee is too old, this will lessen his/her chances of getting a job. Conversely, if a company is very successful in the market, the supply side would be better. Barriers are variables of unfit; they lessen the fit.

On the one side is the organisation which has a demand for workers to fulfil its aims, e.g., to produce something. The organisation offers for this a salary and other benefits and specific work conditions. The worker offers in return his/her work and has several needs that must be fulfilled, i. e., and flexible working hours for a single mother.

A theory is yet to emerge that elucidates all the possible fit combinations related to employees and organisations. The perceptions on both sides demand profound theoretical and empirical research that remains to be carried out.

2.2 Research Overview

In the following section, we discuss the barriers, facilitators and ambiguous factors in our model and cite the research that considers the inclusion of these factors as important in distinguishing between successful unemployed people who find a job, workers and the long-term unemployed. Due to time and space constraints, we do not go into all the factors we analyse. However, almost all of them are discussed in the Discussion section. Moreover, in this first part of our study we only deal with the individual side; we leave out the organisational and societal side.

<p>FACILITATORS Job passion Self-regulation Self-esteem Career Adaptability Social Network/Support</p>	<p>BARRIERS Procrastination Unemployment history Bad health Non-native origin Obligations Depression/Anxiety</p>
<p>Ambiguities Value Age Education Gender</p>	

Figure 2 - PNFJ Model 2021

2.2.1 Facilitators

The job search process can be seen as a strategy to optimise one's skills and opportunities. Therefore, career and non-career factors are relevant in addressing this challenge. Career transitions are smoother when individuals can plan, anticipate change, and react adaptive to internal changes in the organisation and outside (Ebberwein, Krieschok, Ulven & Prosser, 2004).

2.2.1.1 Career Adaptability

Super and Knasel (1981, pp. 198-199) defined the term career adaptability thus: "Each individual should be seen as engaged in the process of finding a balance between acceptance of the pressures that come from the world of work and making his or her impact upon the environment". Savickas & Porfeli, (2012, p. 662) define career adaptability to cope "with current and anticipated tasks, transitions and traumas in their occupational roles that, to some degree large or small, alter their social integration"

With the rapid development of society and technology, personal adaptability is becoming increasingly important. Learning how to adapt to a changing world is becoming an essential condition for success. Career adaptability can help individuals to smoothly adapt to changes when coping with their career roles, and maintain their ability to balance their career roles, which will affect their important psychological resources for career development and achieve more meaning in life. Super and Knasel (1981) argued that career adaptability is a state of readiness required to cope with tasks that can be predicted by current and future job roles and to adapt to unpredictable work or changes in the work environment.

Career adaptability is associated with factors such as "leave or stay" in the organisation. A higher commitment to remain in the organisation could be due to a higher career satisfaction (Chan & Mai, 2015; Guan et al., 2015) and a higher fit with the job and the organisation (Ferreira & Coetzee, 2013; Ferreira et al., 2013). Conversely, other studies aver that adaptable individuals feel less insecure and are aware of their high levels of marketability; therefore, they might leave the organisation or take other chances (Spurk, Kauffeld, Meinecke, & Ebner, 2016).

For unemployed people, career decision-making and career confidence positively predicted reemployment quality 8 months later (Koen et al., 2010).

Career adaptability also had a positive influence on wellbeing in unemployed emerging adults (Konstam et al., 2015). In the study of Maggiori et al., (2013), the unemployed reported higher adaptability resources than the high job-insecurity employed and were comparable to low job insecurity employed. Wellbeing was predicted by adaptability resources. Monteiro et al. (2019) reported that the students with higher levels of concern, control, curiosity, and confidence are more likely to be employed 18 months after the labour market transition. Career adaptability can contribute to the prospects of unemployment, as Klehe et al., (2011) show: in an organisational downsizing, those with high exploratory career adaptability showed higher job-search behaviours and turnover.

Therefore, it is a key success factor to adapt to one's career during employment and plan one's professional future based on one's abilities, to prevent and avoid unemployment.

Individuals who anticipated and planned their careers realistically had better transitions in the job market than those who ignored or planned unrealistically (Super & Knasel, 1981).

2.2.1.2 Self-regulation

The job-seeking process can be a long and a very thorny road to tread. Therefore, self-regulation is needed to overcome the challenges of the job selection process. Various studies stress the importance of self-regulation importance in the job search process, as a factor that heightens the probability of finding a job. Therefore, the job search has been conceptualised as a self-regulatory process. According to Kanfer et al., (2001); Van Hooft et al., (2020), it has greater importance than job-search intensity during the application process.

The relevance of the psychological contract for work performance focuses on the **trait of self-regulation** goal-oriented actions over time. These are “self-generated thoughts, feelings, and actions regarding job search that are planned and cyclically adapted to the attainment of one’s employment goals.” (Karoly, 1993; Zimmerman, 2000). Psychologists usually regard self-esteem as an enduring personality characteristic, though normal, short-term variations can happen: “Locus of control is the belief regarding whether internal or outside forces have control over their success”. An internal locus of control is where people are responsible for what they experience and external outside events are responsible for their lives (Phares, 1991).

These factors play an important role in the job search processes and the relevance of the search intensity needed for higher success. In addition, employment success has to do with application behaviour, longer months in employment before unemployment and higher wages, and finally, unemployment benefits (Andrisani, 1977, 1981; Groves, 2005; Semykina & Linz, 2007; Duncan & Dunifon, 1998).

Contrarily, those with an internal locus of control see future outcomes as being contingent on their own decisions and behaviour. People with an internal locus of control have a high search intensity, higher transition rate from unemployment to work and find a job well rewarded, while those with an external control mechanism believe that search has a small impact on the number of jobs they are offered (Caliendo et al., 2015).

Additional empirical outcome (Kanfer et al., 2001) underlines the role of self-regulation in job search, showing that it positively relates to job-search intensity and quality, and employment success. This means job seekers are rewarded with interviews and finally employment offers, through an intensive job search.

Similarly, a quality study concluded that self-control and self-discipline are decisive indicators individuals must have, to make re-employment possible through their own efforts, rather than expect to get a job through the official channels of work administrations (Demazière, 2020 S. 14).

Training influences peoples’ goal orientation towards job seeking, which in turn would relate to learning from failure, strategy awareness, thus leading to job-search intentions, resulting in turn in increased re-employment status (Noordzij et al., 2012). In a similar study, Berger et al., (2019) found that treatment has a positive effect on the quality of application documents as well as on the probability of participants submitting their

documents on time (behavioural self-regulation). However, they do not find a significant positive effect on labour market reintegration. In a longitudinal study of young job seekers, self-regulation appeared to be more important in predicting resume submissions and first interviews, whereas positive emotions (emotional self-regulation) predicted success in obtaining second interviews and job offers. According to Ebberwein et al., (2004), Self-Regulation towards a learning orientation is crucial for job seekers and underlines the importance of their increasing their attractiveness to the labour market by broadening their knowledge with training, further education, or unpaid work, just to get the experience required for areas in which they lack professional experience.

In summary, the whole job search procedure could be seen as an enabling process for self-regulation in different fields such as performing analyses of the labour market for their niche of interest and deducing from this result the suitable further education to close the portfolio gap and improving presentation and networking skills needed to navigate successfully to the desired job. Finally, setbacks are part of the job search process. The process of empowering job seekers was developed by Caplan et al., (1989), who designed a specific job-seeking training plan, empowering job seekers to anticipate, cope with and overcome setbacks and likewise regulate emotions and continue to pursue their goal undeterred. Moreover, many studies highlight the job-seeking period as a learning process (Liu et al., 2014, Da Motta Veiga & Turban, 2014; Hoofst et al., 2013). Therefore, we expect to relate self-regulation positively with a successful job search process.

2.2.1.3 Self-esteem

Self-esteem is an aspect of a proactive personality. Smith and Mackie (2007) defined self-esteem thus: "The self-concept is what we think about the self; self-esteem is the positive or negative evaluations of the self, as in how we feel about it." In this sense, self-esteem is an attractive psychological construct because it predicts certain outcomes, such as academic achievement or happiness. Psychologists usually regard self-esteem as an enduring personality characteristic, though normal, short-term variations can occur.

In the study of Hesketh (1984), the unemployed with high self-esteem and an internal locus of control attributed the failure to lack of effort, while crediting their success to ability. Unemployed people with low self-esteem and an external locus of control attributed success to effort and luck, but failure was not attributed to lack of ability, nor lack of effort, but to task difficulty or bad luck. On the other hand, highly confident job seekers were more efficient in converting interviews into job offers (Moynihan et al., 2003). Conversely, McGee (2014) found no difference between internal and external loci of control in job search and finding a job.

High levels of self-direction, a term closely related to self-esteem, are associated with higher self-evaluation during unemployment (Fryer, 1992). Such an attitude is essential for a successful job search process. Therefore, higher self-esteem generates higher job search activity (Kanfer et al., 2001; Wanberg, Glomb, Song, & Sorenson, 2005). On the other hand, poor self-esteem diminishes a successful job search and employability, (Guindon & Smith, 2002). Self-esteem is also positively related to applicant perceptions of P-J fit. These results are important, as this study and others have found that subjective perceptions of fit are

significantly related to work outcomes (Cable & Judge, 1996; Kristof, 1996). Individuals with high self-esteem have a clear idea of the occupation suitable for their skills and therefore achieve a better P-J Fit. Conversely, individuals with low self-esteem are more likely to choose occupations unsuitable for their abilities (Korman, 1966). A similar relation was found in the study of Keon, Latack, and Wanous (1982), where high self-esteem leads to a fit for self-image and the selection of the Organization Fit and *vice versa*.

Individuals with high self-esteem have a committed, productive attitude within the organisation due to their competencies (Pierce, Gardner, Cummings, & Dunham, 1989) and lower turnover, stress, and reduced likelihood of resigning from the job (Brockner, 1988; Tharenou, 1979).

Job seekers oriented their preferences for organisations from different perspectives. Materialism and self-efficacy are important predictors for the preferences of organisations with high levels of incentives and gratification (Cable & Judge, 1994). Self-esteem and organisational centralisation influence job seekers positively (Turban & Keon, 1993). Supplementary P-O fit has also been found to predict organisational preferences (Tom, 1971).

2.2.1.4 Social capital

2.2.1.4.1 Social capital and job

Labour market-relevant information is not freely available or evenly distributed. Therefore, various researchers study relationships and their influence on job placement and their relevance for personal advancement in the labour market. The more social capital a person has, the more access they have to jobs and higher levels of education (De Silva et al., 2005; Granovetter, 1974, 1973; Lin, 1982; Putnam, 1993), leading to better social and economic opportunities (Albrecht, 2004; Briggs, 1998).

Good contacts and references are important in the job search. Granovetter (1973, 1974) distinguishes between "strong ties" and "weak ties". In network theory, the term strong ties refer to familial and social relationships with a close emotional bond which are easily accessible, whereas weak ties represent acquaintances who have rather loose social relationships with each other. Accordingly, the effectiveness of weak networks thrives on the flow of information established by the trust within the network, in the sense of "the trust in the trust of others". (Putnam, 1993:168). Thus, weak relationships can help job seekers to gain an informational advantage and a hiring advantage in the competition for scarce goods such as jobs (Albrecht, 2004; Bourdieu, 1983, 1987; Coleman, 1990).

Coleman, as a rational choice theorist, and Granovetter shaped the "existence of the network" concept, while Bourdieu as a cultural theorist and Marxist, approaches the topic from a cultural ideological content and context and profound reflection (Szreter, 2002; Tarrows, 1996; Levi, 1996; Fine, 2001). Bourdieu (1983:190-191) defines social capital as the "totality of actual and potential resources associated with the possession of a durable network and more or less institutionalised relations of mutual knowledge or recognition" (. Bourdieu highlights the relevance of social capital, connecting individuals through networks to valuable resources, the size and volume of which are decisive. Being part of the "group" means having access to circulating information that can lead to better positioning in the application process. Thus, social capital can be transformed into other capitals, such as

economic capital (Bourdieu, 1986, 1992:50-51). Further, social capital is of central importance as a resource during unemployment and serves to improve the chances of success of applicants' actions for securing a job (Lin, 2000, 2001; Voss, 2007; Brandt, 2006). It also requires a well-structured network, size, and diversity to provide access to the valuable resource of carrier information necessary to enter the labour market (Granovetter, 1995:105-113, 1973).

Putnam's original view that social capital would be based only on horizontal relationships was soon abandoned and a vertical relationship introduced between different actors in different hierarchical positions (Putnam, 2000:19). According to this, networks exist, on the one hand, that impede the flow of information outwards and enable it inwards ("bonding"); on the other hand, there also exist networks that facilitate the flow of information between inside and outside ("bridging"), serving as social capital and enabling civic integration based on trustworthiness and reciprocity. These two capitals have similarities with Granovetter's strong and weak ties that enable social mobility. An additional "linking" capital can be considered as an extension of bridging social capital involving networks of trusting relationships between individuals and groups who occupy different social strata or hierarchies and are thus in positions of formal or institutionalised political and economic power. This connection enables access to more resources or privileges (Woolcock, 2003; Woolcock, 2001:13-14; Mayoux, 2001).

During the selection process, the strength and the structure of the networks are important factors that can lead to occupational recruitment. Nevertheless, Voss (2007) emphasises the central role the status of an applicant's contact person (weak relationship) has to play in job placement. In this context, the applicant's social capital is strongly influenced by the status of the contact person, who serves as a bridge between the applicant and the employer.

While the under-researched labour selection process is not transparent, not for natives even less for immigrants (Petersen et al., 2000), it is essential to consider the hidden labour market. Inside and outside the organisation, networks influence the attitudes and behaviour of employees. The fact that employees are well networked with co-workers in the organisation predicts a long-term commitment, whereas for employees with a higher membership of external networks, they could be a bridge to a new job (Moynihan & Pandey, 2007).

In Switzerland, Riaño and Baghdadi (2007) found in their study that highly skilled migrants are confronted with a devaluation of their professional competencies that leads to Misfit. In addition, native language proficiency, quality of educational certificates, lack of work experience in the local society, cultural distance, national and international labour market regulations, as well as gender are relevant for finding a job. Only a third of the immigrant women interviewed found a Job-Fit according to their skills, which was however intermittent and short-term, despite having excellent language skills in German, higher educational and professional skills. For low skilled migrants' social networks are significant for finding low occupational status jobs, in comparison to natives, resulting in misfit. This circumstance generated overqualification for migrants (Leschke et al., 2020).

2.2.1.4.2 Social capital in general

Social capital has been the subject of much debate. Social capital has been defined on an individual “micro-level” as well as a systemic “macro-level”. A variety of definitions, dimensions, concepts, and methodologies have been extensively debated in this regard, along with vague conceptualisations and definitions (Hean et al., 2003).

Development issues in the periphery are “structural factors as the flight of real capital, in the first case, and the instability of commodity prices and the presence of exploitative governments, in the second” (Tarrow, 1996; Harriss, 2005). To tackle the implementation of development policies, the World Bank took a closer look at this topic and introduced a new concept, “linking” social capital, to describe the relationships between institutions or people within a societal power hierarchy (Putnam, 1995, 2000). The idea is a powerful instrument of a discourse of depoliticisation that is in fact highly political and where governments should redistribute social and economic resources more equally (Harris, 2001). Therefore, social capital overestimates its potential and not only exaggerates its scope but also downplays the importance of the steps to be taken structurally and politically. Tarrow (1996) has strongly criticised the constructed concept of social capital in general, its analysis and methodological approach.

At the micro-level in recent years, a consensus has emerged that social capital can be assessed by a person's network connections, including size, trustworthiness, resource ownership and reciprocity (Lin & Fu, 2001; Chen et al., 2009). Therefore, we will analyse next the three dimensions for job-seeking purposes: bonding, bridging, and linking social capital.

2.2.2 Barriers

Barriers hinder the probability of getting a job on both sides. If one is sick or depressed, one's appearance is different, as also one's motivation and energy. Employers will not recruit someone with disabilities, low self-esteem, or a long history of unemployment. They attribute it to the person and not to the economy or society. Unemployment negatively affects mental and emotional health. Beyond the negative impact of an economic disaster, COVID-19 presents additional challenges such as fear of the virus itself, collective grief, prolonged physical distancing, and associated social isolation, all of which compound the impact on our collective psyche.

2.2.2.1 Unemployment history

The long-term unemployed are a special group which consists of unskilled workers, aging workforce, people that were made redundant due to organisational restructuring, etc. and whose chances are far worse in the labour market.

The longer unemployment lasts, the poorer mental health becomes (Herber, et al., 2019). A potential explanation is that the long-term unemployed had poor prospects from the outset (heterogeneity), e.g., lower education. A contrasting explanation is that their bad outcomes are a consequence of the extended unemployment they have experienced (state dependence). In their study of census data, Abraham et al., (2016) supports the state dependence hypotheses: even with controls for individual heterogeneity, they found that unemployment duration has a strong negative effect on the likelihood of subsequent

employment. Kroft et al., (2013) experimented by submitting 12,000 invented CVs with similar education, backgrounds, and experience. The only difference was how long the applicant had been without a job. The researchers found that the chances of a candidate being called back by an employer declined progressively as the duration of unemployment grew longer, from 7.4% after one month of unemployment to 45% at the eighth month, where the rate for invitations for a job interview stabilised.

Rothstein (2016) reported that logit estimates from hazard models showed that being black, having lower educational attainment, and having lower cognitive skills were associated with increased odds of having a long-term spell of unemployment in any given month. In the selection of candidates, too much still depends on extraneous factors such as gender, age, or nativity, instead of looking for competencies and skills. And the probability of this is rising because of the use of Artificial Intelligence in the selection process. One can conclude that long-term unemployment is bad for re-employment, but for someone with poor qualifications, it can nearly be hopeless.

Ferreira et al., (2015) show that Individuals who reported a long period of unemployment in the initial assessment but were re-employed at the second assessment showed meaningful gains in positive affect and life satisfaction. Comparatively, those who had a shorter history of unemployment and were re-employed showed a reduction in affect and life satisfaction. The outcomes of other studies (Norström, et al., 2014.) indicate conversely that the impact on health for unemployed immigrants is not evident.

For people facing long-term unemployment, the chances of finding a job diminish as time passes. The consequences are an economic bottleneck, social retraction and resultant degradation of social relations, and loss of status. All these factors exacerbate an entry or re-entry into the labour market.

2.2.2.2 Depression

Unemployment may contribute to depression because of losses in social contact, positive feedback, and status or stress related to income loss. Two meta-analyses show the effect of depression (Paul & Moser, 2009; Kim & von dem Knesebeck, 2016). In the Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System, almost 12% of the emerging adults were depressed and about 23% unemployed. Significantly, more unemployed than employed emerging adults were classified with depression. In the final model, the odds of depression were about 3 times higher for the unemployed than employed emerging adults.

Stolove et al., (2017) showed in their longitudinal study that depression has a negative impact on re-employment. Thus, the chance of re-employment decreases and the risk of persistent unemployment is increased.

General mental ill-health amongst unemployed individuals, migrants, those older than 45, and being financially dependent, was associated with lower levels of re-employment after one year (Skärlund et al., 2012).

Statistically significant increased depression risk was found for unemployed persons receiving means-tested benefits (Zuelke et al., 2018). Long-term unemployed persons had more episodes of a depressive mood in the previous 12 months, compared to the short-term unemployed. The duration of unemployment and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) score had

a positive correlation. The risk of depression increased significantly among the short-term unemployed but not the long-term unemployed when a person had experienced more episodes of unemployment, (Stankunas et al., 2006).

The Cross-sectional results of Mossakowski (2009) suggest that compared to being currently employed, unemployment status and out-of-the-labour-force status were significantly associated with depressive symptoms at ages 29–37 years, independent of demographics, current socio-economic status (SES), family background, and prior depressive symptoms. The relationship between out-of-the-labour-force status and depressive symptoms was stronger for men, because it is more common for women to be out of the labour force, and it may be less stigmatising and psychologically distressing for them, compared to men. The longitudinal analyses revealed that past unemployment duration significantly predicted depressive symptoms, net of demographics, current SES, family background, and prior depressive symptoms. In contrast to the cross-sectional findings, the time spent out of the labour force did not have a significant influence on subsequent depressive symptoms.

Adjusted multiple logistic regression analysis showed that among previously undepressed male workers, workers who went from permanent status to being unemployed (odds ratio: 4.50) and from permanent status to being precarious workers (odds ratio: 3.15) had significantly high levels of new-onset depressive symptoms, compared to those who retained their permanent employment status. There were no significant increases in new-onset depressive symptoms of male workers who went from permanent status to being self-employed or economically inactive. No significant differences were found among female workers (Kim & Park, 2021).

Similar results were shown by another study: generalised estimating equation models showed that employment was associated with lower depressive symptoms. For employed participants, adverse psychosocial work conditions, such as job insecurity, psychological demands, and decision authority were associated with depressive symptoms. For the entire sample, the number of adverse psychosocial working conditions was associated with higher depressive symptoms, while participants working in poor quality jobs reported levels of depressive symptoms similar to those who were unemployed or not in the labour force. This study showed that poor quality employment (as assessed by having many adverse psychosocial work exposures) was associated with a similar level of depressive symptoms as unemployment (Rueda et al., 2015).

Depression is significantly associated with other factors, like being male, long duration of unemployment (≥ 1 year), low self-esteem, and poor social support, as the study of Mokana et al., (2020) with young unemployed demonstrated.

2.2.2.3 Bad health

Hoven et al., (2020) found consistent associations of precarious, discontinuous, or disadvantaged careers with strenuous physical working conditions and with low occupational rewards. These adverse trajectories are defined by threats to the core material and psychosocial needs at work, such as the need for control and autonomy, the need for adequate reward and appreciation, and the need for security and continuity. As these needs are not met for employees working in these trajectories, chronic stressful experiences may

result, with negative effects on their health and wellbeing. This is the opposite of a sustainable job.

In the meta-analyses of McKee-Ryan et al., (2005), unemployed individuals had lower psychological and physical well-being than did their employed counterparts. Unemployment duration and sample type (school leaver vs. mature unemployed) moderated the relationship between mental health and unemployment, but the current unemployment rate and the amount of unemployment benefits did not. Also, psychological stress is reported for unemployed when receiving welfare financial support, “many respondents found their interactions with welfare services were quite negative, characterised by mistrust, surveillance and pressure” is reported in the interview sample of Boland T & Griffin R (2017).

Bad health is a risk factor for job loss or staying unemployed. In the population-based cohort study of adults HEAF in England (aged 50–64 at baseline) employment as road transport drivers/in-vehicle trades (men), or in teaching/education/nursing/midwifery or caring personal services (women), exciting work was more frequent among people for health-related versus non-health-related reasons. Principal socio-demographic and lifestyle risk factors for health-related job loss (HRJL) were: struggling financially (men and women), low physical activity (men), being overweight or obese, and current smoking (women). Mutually adjusted work-related risk factors for HRJL were job dissatisfaction, and inability to cope with the physical or mental demands of work (Sydall et al., 2020).

Having lost the job at the second measurement point was found to be associated with a higher level of health complaints, but only for men. There was no effect on the unemployed at both time points and those unemployed who got a new job at time 2 (Isaakson et al., 2004). Contrarily, (Reine et al., (2008) found that transition from an unstable labour market position to permanent employment could be health-promoting: there is an association between the lower probability of psychological symptoms and obtaining permanent employment as well as having permanent employment, even after controlling for possible confounders and mediators, as well as for an indicator of health-related selection. It is important not to get just any job but a good job, because the prevalence of common mental disorders was similar for respondents who were unemployed and those in the poorest quality jobs. This pattern persisted after controlling for relevant demographic and socio-economic covariates (Butterworth et al., 2013).

Using data from the European social survey (Cortes-Franch et al., 2019) no significant differences in mental wellbeing were found between the unemployed-non-active, unemployed-active, and those working in low-quality jobs in either sex. Only men from conservative countries in low-quality jobs had better mental wellbeing than unemployed-non-active men. Only having a good-quality job reduced the likelihood of poor mental wellbeing, compared to being unemployed (non-active) among men in all countries (except Social-Democratic) and women in Eastern and Southern European countries.

Not only is unemployment detrimental to mental health; having poor-quality job results in significantly worse mental health than unemployment. Factors such as being female, younger age, poorer physical health, not having a partner, having a limited employment

history and financial hardship correlate positively with poor mental health (Butterworth et al., 2011).

2.2.2.4 Burnout

Burnout is a syndrome resulting also from chronic work-related stress, caused by excessive job demands and insufficient job resources, with symptoms characterized by feelings of energy depletion or exhaustion, increased mental distance from one's job, or feelings of negativism or cynicism related to one's job. Job features that contribute to burnout are unclear requirements, impossible requirements, constant high stress without relief, serious consequences of failure, lack of personal control, lack of recognition, poor communication, insufficient compensation, and poor leadership. Professions that deal with people or helping people such as teachers, nurses, or social workers are more prone to burnout (Maslach et al., 1996). Burnout has been on the rise for several years, but more so since the Covid pandemic (Mendoza, 2020). However, recent research has demonstrated that other occupations – including managers, sales representatives, IT specialists, and soldiers – also manifest symptoms of job burnout. In the study of Lin, Jiang, and Lam (2013) with managerial staff as well as the study of Wang et al., (2020) with primary care providers, respondents with a high level of burnout had a high prevalence of turnover intention. The same is true of the study of Scanlan and Still (2019) with mental health personnel using the Job Demands-Resources model.

The direct relationship between motivation and burnout has a solid empirical basis (Cresswell & Eklund, 2005; Li et al., 2013; Van den Berghe et al., 2014). Cresswell and Eklund (2005) posited that amotivation – the least self-determined type of motivation in self-determination theory – presented a strong positive association with burnout and externally regulated motivation, as well as an insignificant relationship with burnout. Moreover, self-determined forms of motivation exhibited significant negative associations with burnout.

2.2.2.5 Procrastination

Online procrastination plays an important role in the lives of the unemployed but has no immediate effects on their perceived job search efforts. Unemployed Internet users with low motivational control struggle more with their job search efforts (Müller et al., 2018). In the study of unemployed persons by Lay and Brokenshire (1997), trait procrastination predicted self-reported job-search behaviours, controlling for initial intentions, with procrastinators exhibiting less job-search activity in the two weeks interval, compared to non-procrastinators. Van den Hee et al., (2020) reported that trait procrastination impairs self-regulatory job search behaviour and subsequent outcomes of the job search. However, job seekers high in trait procrastination can benefit from being autonomously motivated to engage in job search.

Procrastination is also important in the workplace (Nyugen et al., 2013). High levels of procrastination are associated with lower salaries, shorter durations of employment, and a greater likelihood of being unemployed or under-employed, rather than working full-time. Women tend to procrastinate less than men, giving women an employment advantage. In determining the causes of procrastination in the workplace, the results strongly support the gravitational hypothesis: jobs that require higher levels of motivational skills are less likely

to retain procrastinators. Jobs can also foster procrastination: procrastinators tend to have jobs that are lower in intrinsically rewarding qualities.

In the study of Beutel et al., (2016), students and unemployed participants reported higher levels of procrastination compared to employed and retired individuals. Participants with a high self-assessed tendency to procrastinate reported significantly lower incomes.

Procrastination is linked to other concepts, such as job passion. Peixoto et al., (2021) found during the COVID pandemic that academic procrastination is negatively linked to harmonious passion and positively linked to obsessive passion. Academic procrastination in turn is positively linked to psychological distress, whereas harmonious passion is negatively associated with psychological distress.

2.2.2.6 Dark triad

The dark triad comprises the personality traits of narcissism, Machiavellianism, and psychopathy and complements the Big Five on the malevolent side. Machiavellianism is characterised by cynical, pragmatic, misanthropic, and immoral beliefs, emotional detachment, agentic and self-serving motives, strategic long-term planning, manipulation and exploitation, and higher levels of self-interest. Narcissism is an inflated view of self, fantasies about control, success, and admiration, lack of empathy, grandiosity and pride, and the desire to have self-love reinforced by others. Psychopathy is marked by a lack of concern for both, other people and social regulatory mechanisms, impulsivity, selfishness, and a lack of guilt or remorse for harming others. The issue is that many people in leading positions are high on the traits of the dark triad. It is they who decide on who is getting a job, but they tend to discriminate against vulnerable people like the unemployed. Paulhus and Williams (2002)

Prusik and Szulawski (2019) comment that recruiters high in Machiavellianism share a trait with those who score highly in narcissism and psychopathy: they motivate themselves by seeking fun at work. One possible explanation is that the work of recruiters allows them to offer something that others desire. This in turn affords these recruiters a certain amount of power, which might prove appealing for people who want to be flattered and use skills of persuasion and manipulation.

Regarding objective career success, Vollmer et al., (2016) found a positive effect of follower-perceived leader narcissism on subordinates' salary and promotions. Leader psychopathy and leader Machiavellianism were neither related to subordinates' salary, nor the number of promotions. This is due to narcissists continually seeking positive feedback and preferring relationships with persons who affirm their self-esteem, such as persons with positive qualities. It might be that by promoting their subordinates' careers, narcissistic leaders try to retain subordinates to continue receiving admiration from loyal subordinates and/or try to make subordinates feel grateful, to enhance their self-esteem. Other studies show the deleterious effects of narcissistic leaders on their subordinates, resulting in higher employee turnover (Mathieu & Babiak, 2016)

Individuals with a high level of a dark tetrad are more likely to be involved in entrepreneurial action (Cai et al., 2021) and grandiose narcissists often emerge as leaders in organisations, but are no more qualified than non-narcissists (O'Reilly & Pfeffer, 2021).

Furnham et al., (2013) identified that the dark triad is related to the acquisition of leadership positions and interpersonal influence. In a meta-analysis of dark triad and workplace outcomes, Jonason et al., (2012) found that each of the dark triad traits was related to manipulation in the workplace, but each through unique mechanisms. Another meta-analysis found that reductions in the quality of job performance were consistently associated with increases in Machiavellianism and psychopathy and that counter-productive work behaviour was associated with increases in all 3 components of the Dark Triad. However, these associations were moderated by such contextual factors as authority and culture. Multivariate analyses demonstrated that the Dark Triad explains moderate amounts of the variance in counter-productivity, but not job performance (Boyle et al., 2012).

Nguyen et al., (2021) indicated that individuals belonging to the high psychopathy profile reported the lowest levels of job performance, followed by employees belonging to the high Machiavellianism profile and the benevolent profile. The malevolent profile exhibited the highest levels of job performance.

A study of HR showed that Machiavellianism and psychopathy, in general, exert burnout tendencies in both forms (disengagement and exhaustion). However, narcissism is not related to burnout at all, while this is true of Machiavellianism and psychopathy (Prusik & Szulawski, 2019). Leader psychopathy and Machiavellianism were both positively related to follower emotional exhaustion, and leader narcissism was unrelated to follower emotional exhaustion (Vollmer et al., 2016).

Chronic self-promoters (i.e., European-heritage narcissists) were given the most positive evaluations. The narcissism advantage was derived primarily from frequent self-praise and the European-heritage advantage from the use of active ingratiation tactics (Paulus et al., 2013).

2.2.3 Ambiguities

Contrary to barriers, ambiguous factors are those that do not show a linear relationship with finding a job or are broad concepts like personality or attitudes. Even if the unemployment rate is higher among women and higher among older people, there is no linear relationship.

One factor we consider is values. Longitudinal data from a Swedish representative sample (Isaaksson et al., 2004) revealed that work values are stable over 15 months. As expected, the long-term unemployed (mostly active job seekers) had higher measures of work involvement after 15 months. After demographic factors and time 1 measures were controlled for, employment status still had a significant but modest effect on work centrality: being unemployed on both measurement occasions and getting a new job were significantly related to changes in work centrality, although the changes were in the opposite directions. Being unemployed on both occasions was related to generally higher values, whereas there was a negative relationship between work centrality and getting a new job. Tendencies in the same direction were revealed for work involvement and work as entitlement, but none of these was statistically significant. Respondents who were unemployed on both measurement occasions were found to rate work as more important at time 2 than at time 1 for the measures of work involvement and work centrality. Individuals who had been re-employed by time 2 reported lower values on all measures.

2.2.3.1 Big Five

Regarding the Big Five, one can expect more engagement and success in the job-search process for people who are lower on neuroticism (because they are less anxious, self-conscious, and hostile in novel situations and after setbacks), and higher on extraversion (because they are socially interactive and energetic), openness to experience (because they are adaptive and open to trying new methods).

Agreeability, neuroticism, and openness to experience related positively to job search. The effects of agreeability and openness to experience on job search were partially mediated by the array of situational factors, while the effect of neuroticism on job search was fully mediated. The relationship between extraversion and job search became significant in the presence of situational factors, suggesting a suppressor effect. Concerning separation, a similar suppressor effect was found for extraversion (Boudreau et al., 2001). Azarashk et al., (2015) found that neuroticism was higher in unemployed persons, while extraversion, agreeability, and conscientiousness were lower. Openness resulted in no significant difference between employed and unemployed people. Extraversion had a moderating effect on the job search self-efficacy–job search success relationship for more extraverted job seekers (Petruzzello et al., 2021). Extraversion was positively related to success in job interviewing but did not add significantly to predicting successful job interviews after the effects of trait positive affect were removed (Burger & Caldwell, 2000).

In the meta-analyses of Wilmot et al., (2019), extraversion had favourable associations with job application variables. Extraversion had relations in a consistently desirable direction for 21 of 23 variables (91%) like job search success or employment interview. Unemployed people need a lot of structure to find a job, as the study of Van Hooye and Lootens (2013) shows: openness to experience was negatively related to sense of purpose.

Conscientiousness is related positively to sense of purpose, structured routine, effective organisation, and persistence. Neuroticism is related negatively to sense of purpose and present orientation. Proactivity positively predicted structured routine but was a negative predictor of present orientation and persistence.

3 Method

3.1 Study design

The present follow-up study was conducted using samples of employed and unemployed individuals. This is to determine which factors are important and genuine for unemployed people to find a job. After the follow-up in between April 2022 and March 2023, now it is time to analyse which factors differentiate unemployed people at t1 who have found a job from unemployed people who have not found a job. Another comparison will be how the employees who kept their job differentiate from employees who lost their job or who found a new job. In the end the aim is to find the factors that will lead to a sustainable job, for the unemployed and the employed.

In addition, important questions were analysed in depth through face-to-face interviews with line managers, a human resources manager and the unemployed.

3.2 Sample

The data collection for the baseline study (wave 1) took place by means of two online surveys with a first sample between February and April 2021 consisting of unemployed and employed people. The participants were targeted via umbrella organizations for unemployed people and employees: 200 labour action programs from the German, French and Italian part of Switzerland, several labour unions at national level.

The second sample was collected from April to May 2021. Here, data collection took place via a scientific research institute who delivered a panel of 50'000 participants. The third sample consisted only of unemployed people from various unemployment organisations at national level in Switzerland, who filled out the questionnaire in January and February of 2021.

For the follow-up survey (wave 2) only participants from sample 2 and 3 were contacted, as respondents from sample 1 were only few and no longer available. The follow-up survey took place in the spring 2022 for sample 2 and in February and March 2023 for sample 3. The same online questionnaire was used for all samples and in both waves. It took approximately 20 minutes to complete and was available in the four languages: German, English, French and Italian. Table 1 shows the size of the two samples and two measurement points. Among the people that participated in wave 1, 39.8% participated also in wave 2.

In this document, the designation t1 is used for wave 1 and t2 for wave 2.

3.3 Questionnaire

We constructed a questionnaire according to our model. Emphasis was on standardized scales and short scales. For the second survey of unemployed people from the PES, we included new concepts such as breaching and performance in the questionnaire.

3.3.1 Sociodemographic variables

Age, gender, country of origin, migrant status, social obligations, children

3.3.2 Personality

1. **Big Five:** BFI-2_XS. (Lang et al., 2011).
2. **Self-Regulation.** Pichardo et al., Subscale perseverance, Goal-setting, 1 item learning from mistakes, 4 Items goal-setting
3. **Procrastination** (Svartdal & Steel, 2017)
4. **Dark Triad** (Küfner et al., 2015)
5. **Self-esteem** (von Collani & Herzberg, 2003)

3.3.3 Job-related questions

1. **Education**
2. **Profession**
3. **Unemployment history (unemployment frequency rate, i.e., number of unemployment periods)**
4. **Reasons for dismissal**
5. **Application behaviour**
6. **Person-job-fit person-organisation fit** (Ardıç et al., 2016; Saks & Ashforth, 1997)
7. **Person-Supervisor-Fit** (Cable & DeRue, 2002)
8. **Career adaptability** (Maggiori et al., 2017)
9. **Commitment** (Mowday et al., 1979)
10. **Job Passion** (Vallerand et al., 2003). Subscale obsessive passion 7.
11. **Psychological breaching** (Robinson & Wolfe Morrison, 2000). 5 Items with highest factor loadings
12. **Job performance** (Yousef, 2000)

3.3.4 Social networks

1. **Social capital** (X. Chen et al., 2009)
2. **Social Support** (Kliem et al., 2015)
3. **Size social networks**
4. **Loneliness** (Hays & DiMatteo, 1987)

3.3.5 Health

1. **Depression-Anxiety.** (Löwe et al., 2010)
2. **Burnout** (Riley et al., 2018)
3. **Psychological and physical health**

3.4 Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 have higher scores in facilitators at t1 than unemployed people who remained unemployed.

Hypothesis 2: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 have lower scores in barriers at t1 than unemployed people who remained unemployed.

Hypothesis 3: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 are different in sociodemographic factors at t1 compared to unemployed people who remained unemployed.

Hypotheses 4: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 have higher scores in job-related variables at t1 than unemployed people who remained unemployed.

Hypothesis 5: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 have more facilitators and less barriers at t1 than unemployed people who remained unemployed.

Hypothesis 6: People who are employed both at t1 and t2 differ in facilitators and barriers at t2 to former unemployed who found a job by t2.

4 Quantitative results

The present data were analysed using Statistical Software for Social Science IBM SPSS 29.0. For inference statistics we used analyses of variance (ANOVA) to test potential differences, people with different employment status, Chi-squared tests for associations between categorical variables and logistic regression analyses to test associations between predictors and the criterion variable whether or not (yes | no) participants found employment at t2 and Chi-squared test was used to test frequency and distribution among some categorical variables. To confirm or reject defined hypotheses, we used alpha values at the level of 0.05.

4.1 Analysis of one-time participants and two-time participants

We used analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test if one-time participants and two-time participants were comparable in all important variables. There were highly significant differences between people who took part in both surveys and people who took part only in one survey. People, who took part in both surveys had:

- Higher values in the dark triad personality traits narcissism and macchiavellism, and lower values in psychopathy
- Lower career adaptability confidence and curiosity
- Higher loneliness, higher social capital quantitative
- Higher procrastination
- Higher age, higher education level, a higher percentage of Swiss citizenship

Only significant at 5% were:

- Higher depression
- Higher self-esteem, higher self-regulation goal
- Higher job passion, lower job commitment
- Higher social capital qualitative

The returning and non-returning participants did not differ significantly in their initial job status (employed, unemployed and house wife/husband). 49.8% of the unemployed took part a second time.

48.7% of sample 2 took part in both measurement points, but only 31.9% of sample 3. This difference is highly significant ($\chi^2 = 98.69$; $p < .001$).

Table 1: Number of participants in the two samples, according to participation in one or 2 waves

	Only t1	Both measurement points: t1 + t2
Sample 2	812	770
Sample 3	1221	572
Total	2033	1342

Table 2: Transition matrix, total sample, from t1 to t2

Status at t2	Frequency	Percentage
Stayed employed	343	25.7
Stayed unemployed	221	16.5
Stayed other	70	5.2
Changed from employed to unemployed	11	0.8
Changed from employed to other	31	2.3
Changed from unemployed to employed	520	38.9
Changed from unemployed to other	132	9.9
Changed from other to employed	8	0.6
Total	1336	100.0

As Table 2 shows, almost 40% of people changed from unemployed to employed, but we oversampled unemployed. 16.5% stayed unemployed, 9.9% switched to the other category. Less than 1% of previously employed people got unemployed. Also, less than 1% changed from other to employment.

Of those formerly unemployed who found a job in sample 3 and answered the question this is the distribution of reasons for finding the job (Table 3).

Table 3: Reasons for finding a job, sample 3

Own Skills	206	34.62%
Networks	95	15.97%
Further Education	75	12.61%
Support from the PES	44	7.39%
Other reasons	48	8.07%
Not answered	258	43.36%

According to people's subjective view, the most important reason to find a job are their own skills, second are social networks and third further education.

4.2 Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis 1: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 have higher scores in facilitators at t1 than unemployed people who remained unemployed.

To test hypothesis 1, we used a logistic regression model with the facilitators as independent variables, in order to examine statistically significant predictors that differentiate between people that were successful and people that were not successful in finding a job. Table 4 gives an overview over the statistical results for all predictors.

The Hosmer-Lemeshow-Test showed a χ^2 (df=8) = 2.982, and a significance of p=.935. The model is highly significant with a χ^2 (10) =24.477, the Nagelkerke² is .060.

Table 4: Results of the logistic regression for hypothesis 1

Indicator	Regressions coefficient	Standard error	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Selfregulation_Goal	0.315	0.141	4.964	0.026	1.370
Selfregulation_Perseverance	-0.053	0.181	0.085	0.771	0.949
Career Adaptability-Concern	0.085	0.149	0.325	0.569	1.089
Career Adaptability-control	0.393	0.156	6.372	0.012	1.481
Career Adaptability-curiosity	0.120	0.189	0.403	0.526	1.127
Career Adaptability-confidence	-0.151	0.194	0.600	0.439	0.860
Selfesteem	-0.030	0.183	0.027	0.870	0.971
Social Support	-0.293	0.229	1.632	0.201	0.746
Social Capital Quantitative	0.155	0.111	1.948	0.163	1.167
Social Capital Qualitative	0.229	0.126	3.308	0.069	1.258
Constant	-1.689	0.985	2.938	1	0.087

The logistic regression shows that career adaptability control and self-regulation goal are the significant predictors differentiating previously unemployed people who found a job and who remained unemployed.

In the end we confirm hypothesis 1 only partially. Higher values in career adaptability control and self-regulation are associated with a higher likelihood of finding employment. The other facilitators have no significant effect on finding employment.

4.3 Hypothesis 2

Hypotheses 2: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 have lower scores in barriers at t1 than unemployed people who remained unemployed.

Table 5 shows an overview about all variables that we included in a logistic regression to explore what variables are the most important barriers that differentiate between unemployed people who found a job and who remained unemployed.

The Hosmer-Lemeshow-Test showed a χ^2 (df=8) = 7.239, and a significance of p=.511 that the fit is good. The model is highly significant with a χ^2 (df=11) =56.229, the Nagelkerke² is .128.

Higher values in procrastination and anxiety, less loneliness, good physical health and good psychic health were significant predictors of finding employment. We confirmed hypothesis 2 only partially: Bad physical or psychic health as well as loneliness are hindrances to finding a job. However, anxiety and procrastination can, as long as they don't impinge on physical

and mental health or are associated with loneliness, actually improve chances of finding employment. No evidence for an association with finding a job was found for nationality and the frequency of former unemployment episodes.

Table 5: Results of the logistic regression for hypothesis 2

Indicators	Regression coefficientB	Standard Error	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Dark Triad: Macchiavellism	-0.014	0.062	0.054	0.816	0.986
Dark Triad: Narcissism	0.036	0.051	0.486	0.486	1.036
Dark Triad: Psychopathy	0.031	0.061	0.266	0.606	1.032
Anxiety	0.278	0.086	10.435	0.001	1.321
Depression	-0.088	0.097	0.831	0.362	0.916
Loneliness	-0.440	0.177	6.218	0.013	0.644
Bad physical Health	-0.389	0.126	9.507	0.002	0.678
Bad psychic Health	-0.309	0.146	4.492	0.034	0.734
Procrastination	0.412	0.121	11.536	0.001	1.510
Swiss vs. Migrant	0.268	0.203	1.744	0.187	1.307
Frequency of unemployment Episodes	0.050	0.079	0.412	0.521	1.052
Constant	1.437	0.438	10.782	0.001	4.210

Because loneliness is an important predictor for physical and psychic health, we looked at their descriptive statistics at both (table 6). Loneliness increased significantly over time ($p < .001$), physical health worsened less, but still significantly ($p = .043$) and psychic health shows no significant change ($p = .436$). There was no difference in changes over time between the people that found and did not find a job. For both, loneliness and physical health worsen over time, psychic health not at all. In loneliness and physical health those who found a job had better values across both measurement time points than those who stayed unemployed.

Table 6: Mean values in loneliness and health for t1 and t2 for those who found a job and stayed unemployed

	Remained unemployed		Found a job	
	t1	t2	t1	t2
Loneliness	2.00	2.16	1.87	1.92
Bad physical health	2.45	2.54	2.08	2.18
Bad psychic health	2.40	2.47	2.09	2.09

Making an extreme group comparison of those with bad physical health, bad psychic health, or high levels of loneliness, we found the following results:

- Of the people who stayed unemployed 15.7% had bad or very bad mental health at t1 and 17.7% at t2, of those who found a job 6.9% at t1, 7.9% at t2.
- Of the people who stayed unemployed 16.2% had bad or very bad physical health at t1, and 17.2% at t2, of who found a job 7.0% at t1 and 6.9% at t2.
- Loneliness: stay unemployed t1: 14.2%, t2: 20.5%, successful: t1: 9.4% t2: 12.2%.
- All three indicators: 2.3% of the stay unemployed at t1 and t2, 1% and 0.8% of the successful. In all the others 0.9% and 0.2%.

Fortunately, only a small percentage is in the high-risk group for all three indicators: 2.3% at both t1 and t2 of people, that did not find a job, 1% and 0.8% of people that did and 0.9% and 0.2% of all others.

We did the same with anxiety and procrastination, which unexpectedly showed a positive effect on finding a job (Table 7). Procrastination significantly increased over time ($p=.017$), anxiety did not change across both groups ($p=.355$), but there was an interaction effect with group ($p = .045$). ($p=.355$), but there was an interaction effect with group ($p=.045$). Those who found a job had a slightly higher anxiety at t1, but it was lower at t2, whereas in the group that stayed unemployed the opposite is the case.

Table 7: Mean values in procrastination and anxiety for t1 and t2 for those who found a job and stayed unemployed

	stay unemployed		found a job	
	t1	t2	t1	t2
Anxiety	0.8939	1.0056	0.9332	0.8920
Procrastination	2.0727	2.2281	2.2890	2.3444

4.4 Hypothesis 3

Hypothesis 3: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 are different in sociodemographic factors at t1 compared to unemployed people who remained unemployed.

We conducted a binary logistic regression with sociodemographic variables as predictors to see which variables are most important to differentiate between successfully employed people and those that remained unemployed (Table 8).

The Hosmer-Lemeshow-Test showed a $\chi^2(df=8) = 10.650$ and a significance of $p=.222$ that the fit is good. The model is highly significant with a $\chi^2(df=4) = 42.648$, the Nagelkerke² is .081.

All sociodemographic variables had a significant effect on finding a job. Age had the strongest effect on finding a job, followed by education, sex and migrant status. Being younger, having a better education, being of Swiss nationality and of female gender increases the chance of getting a job. Therefore hypothesis 3 can be fully confirmed.

Table 8: Results of the logistic regression for hypothesis 3

Indicator	Regression coefficientB	Standard error	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Age	-0.032	0.007	18.726	0.000	0.969
Sex	0.467	0.170	7.536	0.006	1.595
Education Level	0.143	0.046	9.775	0.002	1.153
Swiss vs. Migrant	0.374	0.179	4.364	0.037	1.453
Constant	0.830	0.509	2.654	0.103	2.293

4.5 Hypothesis 4

Hypotheses 4: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 have higher scores in job-related variables at t1 than unemployed people who remained unemployed.

We conducted a binary logistic regression with job-related variables as predictors to see which variables are most important to differentiate between previously unemployed people that were successful and those that were unsuccessful in finding employment (Table 9).

The Hosmer-Lemeshow-Test showed a $\chi^2(df=8) = 2.455$ and a significance of $p=.964$ that the fit is good. The model is not significant with a $\chi^2(df=4) = 1.670$, the Nagelkerke² is .004.

None of the job-related variables could significantly predict the chances of finding employment.

Table 9: Results of the logistic regression: role of Job-related variables in predicting unemployed people who found a job and who have not found a job by t2

Indicator	Regressions coefficientB	Standard Error	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Job passion	0.028	0.078	0.132	0.716	1.029
Job commitment	-0.002	0.084	0	0.985	0.998
PJFit	-0.158	0.134	1.386	0.239	0.854
POFIT	0.131	0.142	0.858	0.354	1.14
Constant	0.897	0.516	3.028	0.082	2.453

4.6 Hypothesis 5

Hypothesis 5: Unemployed people who have found a job by t2 have more facilitators and less barriers at t1 than unemployed people who remained unemployed.

We tested the variables who were significant or were theoretically relevant in an overall logistic regression model to see which variables significantly predict employment status at t2 independent of all other variables.

The two individual samples (sample 2 and 3) were considered first. Sample 2 consists of self-declared unemployed people, sample 3 of unemployed people who were registered at the PES.

In sample 2, 46.2% of the variance of employment status could be explained (Nagelkerke $R^2 = .004$, $\chi^2(8) = 3.857$, $p = .870$) and in sample 3, 20.5% (Nagelkerke $R^2 = .205$, $\chi^2(x) = 9.940$, $p = .296$). Therefore, in both samples the model was significantly better in predicting unemployment status than a model without any predictors ($p < .001$).

In sample 2 (table 10) education was the best predictor, followed by gender, career adaptability control, age, loneliness, anxiety, and psychic health. All other predictors showed no significant association with employment status. Having a better education, being of female gender, being younger, having a higher control of career planning, a better psychic health and less loneliness and be more anxious were the indicators in sample 2 that lead unemployed people to a job.

Table 10: Results of the multiple logistic regression analysis for sample 2

Indicator	Regression coefficientB	Standard error	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Dark Triad: Macchiavellism	-0.159	0.112	2.030	0.154	0.853
Dark Triad: Narcissm	-0.034	0.100	0.117	0.732	0.966
Dark Triad: Psychopathy	0.134	0.125	1.152	0.283	1.143
Anxiety	0.379	0.181	4.408	0.036	1.462
Depression	-0.300	0.189	2.528	0.112	0.741
Procrastination	0.118	0.274	0.186	0.666	1.125
Selfesteem	0.038	0.593	0.004	0.949	1.039
Selfregulation_goal	0.453	0.363	1.561	0.212	1.574
Selfregulation_perseverance	-0.709	0.398	3.172	0.075	0.492
Career Adaptability-concern	0.194	0.369	0.276	0.600	1.214
Career Adaptability-control	1.160	0.409	8.034	0.005	3.190
Career Adaptability-curiosity	-0.651	0.466	1.952	0.162	0.522
Career Adaptability-confidence	0.003	0.448	0.000	0.995	1.003
Job passion	0.231	0.188	1.518	0.218	1.260
Job commitment	0.177	0.203	0.761	0.383	1.194
PJFit	-0.485	0.317	2.345	0.126	0.616
POFIT	0.326	0.335	0.947	0.330	1.385
Loneliness	-0.927	0.397	5.449	0.020	0.396
Social Support	-0.569	0.320	3.165	0.075	0.566
Social Capital Quantitative	0.481	0.373	1.664	0.197	1.617
Social Capital Qualitative	0.042	0.326	0.017	0.897	1.043
Bad physical health	-0.259	0.269	0.932	0.334	0.772
Bad psychic health	-0.648	0.326	3.958	0.047	0.523
Age	-0.054	0.019	7.830	0.005	0.947
Sex	1.359	0.465	8.535	0.003	3.890
Education Level	0.393	0.133	8.741	0.003	1.482
Swiss vs. Migrant	0.327	0.487	0.451	0.502	1.387
constant	1.691	3.012	0.315	0.574	5.427

In sample 3 (table 11) only three predictors showed a significant association with employment status: Procrastination, Career adaptability concern, and psychic health. All other variables did not significantly differentiate between the unemployed who were successful and those who were unsuccessful in finding a job.

Table 11: Results of the multiple logistic regression analysis for sample 3

Indicator	Regression coefficient B	Standard error	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Dark Triad: Macchiavellism	0.099	0.138	0.517	0.472	1.104
Dark Triad: Narcissm	0.097	0.080	1.491	0.222	1.102
Dark Triad: Psychopathy	-0.113	0.093	1.465	0.226	0.893
Anxiety	0.247	0.123	4.030	0.045	1.280
Depression	-0.057	0.140	0.166	0.684	0.945
Procrastination	0.608	0.211	8.306	0.004	1.837
Selfesteem	-0.399	0.432	0.856	0.355	0.671
Selfregulation_goal	-0.370	0.265	1.944	0.163	0.691
Selfregulation_perseverance	-0.129	0.304	0.180	0.671	0.879
Career Adaptability-concern	0.662	0.236	7.895	0.005	1.938
Career Adaptability-control	-0.413	0.308	1.795	0.180	0.662
Career Adaptability-curiosity	-0.196	0.297	0.432	0.511	0.822
Career Adaptability-confidence	-0.390	0.286	1.855	0.173	0.677
Job passion	-0.091	0.117	0.614	0.433	0.913
Job commitment	-0.128	0.131	0.944	0.331	0.880
PJFit	-0.118	0.200	0.348	0.555	0.889
POFIT	0.049	0.212	0.054	0.817	1.050
Loneliness	-0.337	0.312	1.170	0.279	0.714
Social Support	0.159	0.184	0.744	0.388	1.172
Social Capital Quantitative	-0.072	0.225	0.103	0.748	0.930
Social Capital Qualitative	0.047	0.179	0.070	0.791	1.049
Bad physical health	-0.177	0.187	0.897	0.343	0.838
Bad psychic health	-0.508	0.215	5.590	0.018	0.601
Age	-0.022	0.013	2.761	0.097	0.978
Sex	0.318	0.274	1.345	0.246	1.375
Education Level	0.032	0.079	0.164	0.686	1.033
Swiss vs. Migrant	0.341	0.292	1.367	0.242	1.407
Constant	5.900	2.531	5.433	0.020	365.103

Merging both samples, 22.3% (Nagelkerke $R^2 = .223$) of the variance of employment status could be explained. The model was significantly better in predicting unemployment status than a model without any predictors (Hosmer-Lemeshow-Test $\chi^2(8) = 9.272$, $p = .320$).

Table 12: Results of the multiple logistic Regression analysis for both samples

Indicator	Regression coefficient B	Standard error	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Dark Triad: Macchiavellism	-0.021	0.065	0.106	0.744	0.979
Dark Triad: Narcissm	0.031	0.055	0.308	0.579	1.031
Dark Triad: Psychopathy	-0.024	0.065	0.132	0.717	0.977
Anxiety	0.234	0.093	6.390	0.011	1.264
Depression	-0.109	0.102	1.145	0.285	0.896
Procrastination	0.340	0.149	5.170	0.023	1.404
Selfesteem	-0.361	0.301	1.440	0.230	0.697
Selfregulation_goal	0.034	0.180	0.036	0.850	1.035
Selfregulation_perseverance	-0.105	0.203	0.265	0.607	0.901
Career Adaptability-concern	0.430	0.177	5.918	0.015	1.538
Career Adaptability-control	0.198	0.219	0.814	0.367	1.218
Career Adaptability-curiosity	-0.384	0.228	2.840	0.092	0.681
Career Adaptability-confidence	-0.171	0.220	0.606	0.436	0.843
Job passion	0.025	0.090	0.080	0.778	1.026
Job commitment	-0.018	0.099	0.032	0.858	0.982
PJFit	-0.162	0.153	1.127	0.288	0.850
POFIT	0.134	0.163	0.670	0.413	1.143
Loneliness	-0.538	0.217	6.138	0.013	0.584
Social Support	-0.071	0.144	0.245	0.621	0.931
Social Capital Quantitative	0.174	0.176	0.974	0.324	1.190
Social Capital Qualitative	0.108	0.145	0.557	0.455	1.114
Bad physical health	-0.289	0.138	4.345	0.037	0.749
Bad psychic health	-0.392	0.161	5.933	0.015	0.676
Age	-0.032	0.010	9.756	0.002	0.969
Sex	0.534	0.213	6.282	0.012	1.706
Education Level	0.100	0.062	2.631	0.105	1.105
Swiss vs. Migrant	0.421	0.230	3.368	0.066	1.524
Constant	2.947	1.673	3.103	0.078	19.055

Among the significant predictors, the strongest evidence for predicting employment status was found for age, followed by anxiety, gender, loneliness, psychic health, career adaptability concern, procrastination, and physical health. The better the psychic health, the younger, the higher career adaptability concern, the less lonely, the more anxious and the more procrastinating the higher is the probability of an unemployed person to find a job. Furthermore, women have a higher probability of a finding a job than men. Depression, education level, migration and social support did not have a significant association with employment status.

4.7 Hypothesis 6

Hypothesis 6: people who are employed at t1 and t2 differ in facilitators and barriers at t2 from formerly unemployed who found a job.

Those people who have a job are a good example what factors are important in getting and keeping a job. Our baseline study² showed significant differences between unemployed and employed people. However, the causal direction of the association of employment and relevant predictor variables is not clear. For example, do I have a job because I have high self-esteem or do I have high self-esteem because I have a job? Questions on causal relationships can only be answered in a longitudinal study.

For a former unemployed person, it is important to keep their job. Therefore, we need to look at similarities and differences between newly employed people and those that have been employed for a longer period of time. Table 13 shows the results of the analysis of variance comparing new and long-term employed people.

Table 13: Results of the variance analysis comparing the persons which were employed at t1 and t2 to the newly employed at t2

ANOVA	F	Sig.
Dark Triad: Macchiavellism	103.154	0.000
Dark Triad: Narcissism	42.951	0.000
Dark Triad: Psychopathy	86.888	0.000
Anxiety	0.093	0.760
Depression	0.976	0.323
Procrastination	7.040	0.008
Selfregulation_goal	7.206	0.007
Selfregulation_perseverance	6.200	0.013
Career Adaptability-concern	4.733	0.030
Career Adaptability-control	0.123	0.726
Career Adaptability-curiosity	2.440	0.119
Career Adaptability-confidence	6.656	0.010
Job Passion	12.775	0.000
Job Commitment	8.085	0.005
PJFit	9.508	0.002
POFIT	27.446	0.000
Selfesteem	17.019	0.000
Loneliness	8.099	0.005
Social Support	14.965	0.000
Social Capital Quantitative	2.900	0.089
Social Capital Qualitative	0.982	0.322
Physical Health	0.165	0.685
Psychic Health	0.008	0.927
Age	7.125	0.008
Sex	6.576	0.011
Education	9.517	0.002
Native vs. Migrant	30.469	0.000

² WP2 Labour Market Metricisation: Initial baseline study, final version July 31, 2021.

As table 13 and figure 2 show the newly employed people have significantly lower values in the three Dark Triad scales as well as the job-related scales like P-J-Fit, P-O-Fit, job commitment and job passion, but higher values in career adaptability, social support, and self-esteem. In self-regulation perseverance they have higher values, but in self-regulation goalsetting their values are lower.

There are no differences in all the physical and psychic health scales and in the social capital characteristics.

Figure 2: Comparison of newly and formerly employed persons in facilitators and barriers at t1

As Figure 3 shows that at the second measurement point there are only a few remaining differences between newly employed and long-term employed: the two dark triad scales, anxiety and P-J-Fit.

Figure 3: Comparison of newly and formerly employed persons in facilitators and barriers at t2

Some scales were only used with the employed people: burnout, breaching and Person-Supervisor-Fit. These variables are relevant for a sustainable job.

A further question is, whether certain jobs imply a higher probability for a sustainable employment. In the present sample there was not much variation in the job classification: overrepresented in the employed group were teaching professionals, business, and administration associate professionals; underrepresented were sales workers.

Burnout is regarded as a modern phenomenon and is a frequent reason for a longer sick leave. Figure 4 shows the distribution.

Figure 4: Distribution of the burnout-scale exhaustion in employed people at t2

The distribution of burnout exhaustion in employed people at t2 (Figure 4) shows that many of the them are not exhausted at work. Only a few a high value in exhaustion.

Figure 5: Distribution of the burnout-scale cynicism in employed people at t2

The distribution of burnout cynicism in employed people at t2 (figure5) shows that middle or high values burnout cynicism are very rare in the present sample.

Concerning At t2

Figure 6: Distribution of the burnout-scale accomplishment in employed people

The opposite is true for burnout accomplishment (figure 6). More than half of the respondents have average or high scores.

Does the kind of profession had anything to do with burnout, P-S-Fit and breaching? The higher the position in the ISCO job classification the higher the PS-Fit. This is not necessarily so cause even in low ranks it is important to have a good relationship with your supervisor. A significant relationship is also true for burnout accomplishment, as the following table 14 shows.

Table 14: Association between profession and P-S-Fit, breaching and burnout

	F	Sig.
P-S-Fit	2.247	0.023
Breaching	0.693	0.698
Burnout exhaustion	0.559	0.812
Burnout cynism	1.136	0.337
Burnout accomplishment	2.897	0.004

Employed people, who had a high level of breaching changed highly significantly to unemployment (F=7.29; p=.001).

The burnout scales are the highest for the employed people who changed to the other status. 13% were in the highest group of exhaustion, 8.1% in cynicism. 53.0% were in the low category, 70.0% in cynicism were low. Concerning accomplishment 20.4% had a low score, that is more like burnout, 18.5% had a high score.

If you terminate your job this can be very fair or unfair. There should be associations with the three scales. Only two were significant: P-S-Fit (F=3.22; p=.023) and burnout accomplishment (F=3.74; p=.012). There are trends that the P-s-Fit was the highest in people who get fired but this was very fair. Interestingly the burnout accomplishment was the highest in people with a very unfair job termination (M=4.97), but also high in the very fair group (M=4.89). Astonishingly there was no association with the other burnout scales and breaching.

We compared the scores for both measurement points (Table 15). The scores were nearly identical. Not much change was expected, if you do not change the job.

Table 15: Comparing the two measurement points in breaching, burnout and PS-Fit

	Mean t1	SD t1	Mean t2	SD t2	F	p
Breaching	2.37	0.98	2.38	0.98	0.30	.863
Burnout Exhaustion	3.16	1.61	3.31	1.72	3.21	.074
Burnout Cynism	2.41	1.52	2.53	1.55	2.17	.142
Burnout Accomplishment	4.59	1.73	4.85	1.61	6.79	.010
P-S-Fit	4.36	1.47	4.34	1.33	0.08	.744

Table 16 shows the associations of breaching burnout and PS-Fit with other variables, mostly that are important. Interestingly breaching, burnout exhaustion and burnout cynism correlate with all other variables negative but not with self-regulation goal setting. For burnout accomplishment and PS-Fit it is the other way round: all correlations are positive except self-regulation goal setting. If you suffer from breaching und burnout you have to set new goals, if there is a good fit with the superior and you feel accomplished in the company there is no need to set new goals.

Table 16: Correlations of breaching, burnout and PS-Fit in employed people at t1 and t2

		commitment	PJFit	POFIT	selfregulation_goalsetting	selfregulation_persistence	Career Adaptability-Concern	Career Adaptability-control	Career Adaptability-curiosity	Career Adaptability-confidence	social support	Selfesteem
breaching	Pearson-correlation	-0.511	-0.374	-0.519	0.170	-0.170	-0.051	-0.180	-0.111	-0.130	-0.235	-0.288
	significance	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.168	0.000	0.003	0.000	0.000	0.000
burnout exhaustion	Pearson-correlation	-0.264	-0.279	-0.329	0.342	-0.134	-0.127	-0.179	-0.156	-0.162	-0.190	-0.378
	significance	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
burnout cynism	Pearson-correlation	-0.174	-0.227	-0.238	0.313	-0.190	-0.117	-0.240	-0.181	-0.225	-0.243	-0.390
	significance	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
burnout accomplishment	Pearson-correlation	0.329	0.287	0.243	-0.101	0.301	0.198	0.209	0.224	0.232	0.135	0.244
	significance	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.007	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
PSFIT	Pearson-correlation	0.581	0.362	0.474	-0.092	0.233	0.190	0.149	0.172	0.153	0.306	0.238
	significance	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.012	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

A logistic regression showed that no variable differentiates if somebody stayed employed, got unemployed or changed to the other category. But there were not enough cases in the unemployed and the other group to represent the results.

5 Qualitative results

This qualitative research is mainly based on the ideas of the sociologist Kurt Lewin. He developed his field theory of behaviour in Germany and later in the USA. He differentiated his theory, illustrated it in mathematical terms and developed models for it. For Kurt Lewin, an understanding of the human behaviour was only possible within a context and as a part of a continuum. By "field" he meant the contextuality of human action, and therefore the images and ideas that the actors form about the context, perceptions of the self and of the environment, are of central importance. Developmental dynamics arise in the (social) field through changes in perception; these lead to changes in behaviour (Lewin K., 1963).

5.1 Career Adaptability

5.1.1 Line Manager and HR

Question: To what extent is the employee's career adaptability relevant to the company?

Line Manager 1 – Martin Field: Consulting	Human Resources – Susanne Field: Industry	Line Manager 2 – Jafles Field: Industry	Line Manager 3 – Alessandra Field: Industry
The relevance of CA is high. Issues are much more interconnected than in the past. The pace of change is increasing. This adaptability is therefore extremely important for us. We have been able to achieve this through training and development, but also through acquisitions of new skills and capabilities. We also expect our employees to be able to adapt to new circumstances, such as new supply chains in the wake of the crisis in Ukraine and so on. Curiosity and self-confidence are extremely important drivers for high performance in consulting to other companies.	Curiosity is important in a professional career, regardless of what position you are in. Without it, you cannot be efficient and successful in the future. Strong self-confidence is also very important, without it you will not survive. We have a six-monthly assessment for the performance management of our employees. We have agreed on specific statements. One of them is curiosity. Individual goals are taken into account every year for a specific position. We offer people opportunities to get more experience in different internal jobs, external training to get some skills and coaching. It is important that they develop their skills and are attractive to the market.	My expectation is that people must be capable, not only cognitively, but also in terms of their willingness to learn about other areas. Yes, this means that a person who is mainly responsible for negotiating contracts is also able to take on other tasks for a short time or longer. People must be proactive and send a signal to management that are ready to do more different things, in other words to take control.	Employees can have a successful career in our company as long as they are curious and open to new challenges and new opportunities. Curiosity is very important and having a track record that makes them confident that they can succeed in different environments. Performance is a key indicator and they need be confident that they can make it.

*Career Adaptability (CA): **Concern** entails looking ahead and planning for the future, while **control** reflects a personal responsibility for shaping the future. **Curiosity** is the exploration of possible selves and various roles, and **confidence** is the belief that the individual can implement choices and achieve their goals (Savickas & Porfeli, 2012)]

Summary

Employees' career adaptability is highly relevant given the increasing pace of change in organisations in the technological age. Curiosity and control were mentioned as highly desirable in the interviews and therefore, could be important indicators for an efficient and successful career. In addition, confidence in one's own possibilities and abilities was stated as a very important prerequisite to advance professionally.

Commitment to development in different environments of the company and willingness to internal and external training were mentioned as a must and adaptability as a key factor for good performance.

5.1.2 Unemployed

Questions:

- How do you shape your career?
- Which of the sub-aspects of CA, such as concern, control, curiosity, and trust, are more relevant?

Unemployed 1 - Dubacher	Unemployed 2 - Fabio	Unemployed 3 - Giselle	Unemployed 4 - Betel
Now I am at the end of my professional career, but I am continuing my education and I am very active in the women's network to keep up to date.	I try to follow a certain set of guidelines. My flagship or strategy for my job is an international professional environment that fits in with my life in Switzerland. My career planning is a mixture of vocation, where I feel talented and market demand. I have made a kind of catalogue of job criteria that really reflect the conditions I mentioned.	I worked as an assistant in the back office, where the IT systems are central. So, I took an eight-month course in web design. This gave me a better chance of finding a job. To improve my language skills, I also took German lessons. I leverage my career and adapt it to the requirements.	I am a concerned individual. I am constantly trying to keep up with new frameworks and new technologies. I want to work as a UI developer so I'm trying to get certifications. Curiosity, learning new things, problem solving are more important than knowing theory. When real problems come, how can I fix it? So just to be curious is very important for every aspect of your life.

*[Career Adaptability (CA): Concern entails looking ahead and planning for the future, while control reflects a personal responsibility for shaping the future. Curiosity is the exploration of possible selves and various roles, and confidence is the belief that the individual can implement choices and achieve their goals (Savickas & Porfeli, 2012)].

Summary

Guidelines and strategy to use the career and adapt it to the market requirements seem to be crucial, therefore people concentrate their efforts on learning new frameworks, new technologies, languages, etc. Curiosity was also mentioned as a key factor in shaping the career.

5.2 Social networks

5.2.1 Line Managers and HR

Questions:

- How important are employee networks within the company when it comes to attracting new employees?
- Wich quality do you expect?

Line Manager 1 - Martin	Human Resources - Susanne	Line Manager 2 - Jafles	Line Manager 3 - Alessandra
When employees bring other colleges into the company, some of the risk is removed. The social bond also implies a degree of responsibility. Employees would only recommend good colleagues. And the candidate has a social obligation to the colleagues who are his or her referrers. Employees get a bonus if they recommend someone and the person is hired.	These networks between employees are an important channel for the recruitment of new staff. If you are convinced of a person's quality, you will recommend them. When we have a vacancy, we encourage our employees to post it on their LinkedIn account. We rely on our employees' networks to spread adverts. Sometimes it is very difficult to find people, especially in IT. We have a bonus for successful networking.	This is promoted by strategic HR within the company. The vacancies are promoted within the teams by encouraging them to advertise them through their networks, through employees' LinkedIn or through emails. Getting a bonus for bringing a professional into the company is more specific to our US base, where we have struggled with vacancies for a long time and have not been able to find suitable candidates.	Very important. Employees are encouraged to talk about the company. They repost job adverts on LinkedIn and social networks. It is about the sharing of one's professional life. And for people who are looking to join our company, it is about trying to reach out to colleagues from the company. Employees get a bonus if they recommend someone, a friend and the person is hired. Line managers are not recruited in this way.

Summary

The use of employee networks as a recruitment channel has become very important. Companies are struggling to fill vacancies without finding suitable candidates, especially in sectors such as IT, etc. The social bond implies a certain responsibility and the risk for the company is lower. Employees would only recommend a good colleague, and the candidate would feel socially obliged to the colleague who referred them. Employees receive a bonus if they recommend someone and the person is hired.

5.2.2 Unemployed

Questions:

- Do you use networks for your job search?
- If so, can you report on the quality of these networks?
- How do you foster your networks, what do you value?

Unemployed 1	Unemployed 2	Unemployed 3	Unemployed 4
<p>For my job search, I have connected with a network of businesswomen from all sectors. It is both national and international. There is exchange, we give each other inputs, recommendations, or concrete suggestions.</p>	<p>Yes, I had some professional connections. I used channels like LinkedIn and WhatsApp to let them know about my job search, the situation I was in and what I was looking for. Then they were open and gave me input, contacts, and ideas. This was in terms of contacts that were already in the network, but also contacts that were referrals. I have always tried to meet people in person, because it has a completely different quality to meeting them from a distance or just by email. I met mentors, two handfuls of people, multipliers or gate openers, they opened my eyes, they were effective, I went for a coffee and met them in person. That was a very big advantage because you can see into the inner world of these companies.</p>	<p>I use LinkedIn a lot, but I also go to job fairs and network with companies. I work with employment agencies. It is important to know people who can recommend you, otherwise it is very difficult to get a job. I feel alone. I have no support in this difficult job search.</p>	<p>I have been to a job fair on two occasions and I left my CV there but have not heard anything back. I have also been to a couple of online or face-to-face meeting groups and this has not been successful for me. The quality of the fairs is good, but they should be regular. They explain what they are looking for and are open to discussion, but in the end, they always say it is better to write directly, even if they don't advertise. I have never had a job interview in this kind of way.</p>

Summary

Channels such as LinkedIn are common for job searches. Job fairs, meet-ups - online or face-to-face - are also considered helpful. Getting to know people personally, mentors, multipliers, gate openers are said to be a big advantage in getting an inside of the companies and getting recommended by them. That has been a great help. People feel that they are alone in their search for a job.

5.3 Health

5.3.1 Line Managers and HR

Questions:

- Does your company also hire people with mental or physical disabilities?
- How does your company deal with the health of your employees?
 - What does this mean in terms of health promotion?

Line Manager 1 - Martin	Human Resources - Susanne	Line Manager 2 - Jafles	Line Manager 3 - Alessandra
<p>Yes, we have employees with a physical disability who are in wheelchairs. I do not know of any employees with a mental disability. But I could imagine that it would not be out of question if there is somebody working in the back office. The physical and mental health of our employees is becoming increasingly important. We have various health programmes in place: health check, work-life balance seminars, burnout prevention and reintegration measures for people with burnout. Suggestions on how to cope with the double burden come from new parents. "I have two small children and I have a lot of work, therefore a lot of overtime and how can I have a better work-life balance as a preventive measure? There are ways to reduce the workload or to buy extra leave, unpaid leave, counselling, etc. If we do not have such programmes in place, we will not be attractive in the market to attract the best people.</p>	<p>I am working at the headquarter here in Switzerland and I can talk only for this experience. Physical disabilities are not a problem at all. Concerning mental disability, it is different because we have a lot of pressure in the headquarters. To also protect a sensitive person, this could be the wrong place to work at.</p> <p>We have a health check once a year and we have a sports club. During Corona we offered some support to people who might have had some problems. We are preparing programmes for the future to deal with stress and pressure.</p>	<p>We do have a number of employees with physical disabilities. We have made efforts to be present as a company, especially at disability job fairs. But it is difficult to employ people with mental disabilities.</p> <p>We offer physical and mental health support to our employees. We have health screenings, sports groups (skiing, volleyball, etc.), etc. Many of these activities have been initiated by employees through our Employee Resource Groups (ERGs). At some point they have been adopted by HR and have become sustainable over time.</p>	<p>We do have employees with physical disabilities. Mental disabilities are much more difficult to see, so I do not know to be honest. There are arrangements to help this person to cope with the physical disabilities and as much as possible to welcome the person as if the disability is not a problem. That is what we do, to think beyond the disability of the person.</p> <p>Every year there is a week where the focus is on health. Safety programmes, because of our company's manufacturing plants is a primary concern. There is also a year-round programme with various physical and mental health offers, such as nutrition, eye checks, ergonomics, physical activities, mental health, safety training, support in case of economic problems, etc.</p>

Summary

Physical disabilities of the employees seem to be well integrated in the company policies.

Regarding persons with mental disabilities, the interviewed line managers and HR responsible could not name any persons in their companies.

These companies have a year-round programme with various offers for physical and mental health. Many of these activities have been also initiated by employees' groups.

5.3.2 Unemployed

Questions:

- What about your health, how does it affect your job search?
- Do you feel lonely?
 - If so, what do you do about it?

Unemployed 1	Unemployed 2	Unemployed 3	Unemployed 4
<p>My health is fine so far. I suffer from migraines and have to take great care of myself. I do my part, but the employer must also fulfil their duties. Today is very stressful and we are under a lot of pressure. I take medication to help me cope well with work. If I don't feel well, I go home. I pay attention to my diet, sleep and exercise.</p>	<p>I'm coming from a very difficult situation in terms of mental health, I had a burn-out that lasted for more than 2 years. It had an impact on my job search, it was a killer criterion, if you don't feel centred, nothing works. And amazingly, the turning point started 5 or 6 months ago, but the process to get there was very long. Often it was small first steps that helped: Sending the first email, contacting the first mentor from the network, sending the first application.</p> <p>It was a friendly nudge from people around me, a job coach, a mentor or someone from my circle of acquaintances who knew me well, who supported me and encouraged me to send the first CV, to meet people. Then you start to make progress, from being a victim to being a doer.</p> <p>The loneliness I felt was so great that I almost killed myself. Although I'm very lucky to have a family, a spouse and two children who haven't abandoned me. People from outside have to disturb and help you and not leave you alone.</p>	<p>Spiritual health is also important besides health at all. Sometimes I have no confidence in the process of looking for a job. I say, oh, that's not for me, that's a very senior position. But now I'm learning in this process where I'm more open. I'm encouraging myself to see it as a challenge where I'll learn one or two more things in the senior positions.</p>	<p>When you've applied 200 times and you don't get anything, it's very sad. You start to think you don't have a chance here, you're not good enough. It affects you mentally. But otherwise, I'm healthy and I think I've been tough for so many years. I have friends and I have my family here, so I don't feel lonely. But I do feel lonely when I am looking for work. I'm feeling like nobody really cares.</p>

Summary

Both employees and employers need to be involved when it comes to managing health. Nowadays we are dealing with a very stressful work environment and employees must work under a lot of pressure. Therefore, more action needs to be taken to improve health in companies.

Support from friends and the community is needed in difficult situations. Loneliness needs to be recognized and people around them need to take action.

5.4 Unemployment history

5.4.1 Line Managers and HR

Questions:

- To what extent does a person's unemployment history have an influence on their hiring?

Line Manager 1 - Martin	Human Resources - Susanne	Line Manager 2 - Jafles	Line Manager 3 - Alessandra
<p>It depends on what people have been doing during the time of unemployment. These reasons have to be well explained. We have people who have moved from one country to another and have been unemployed for half a year, had to find their feet in the country, etc.</p> <p>Unemployment due to external factors such as a merger or bankruptcy of the company where people were made redundant is not a problem. Maternity leave, if a woman says "I took 2 years off to raise children" it is an explanation and acceptable. Training and further education are a good reason for a gap. If someone says that they have taken a year or a year and a half off work and have not done any further training, it has a negative connotation. So, I think 6 to 9 months is not a critical period of unemployment.</p>	<p>Gaps must be clearly mentioned. Otherwise, it is not positive, it seems to me that people are trying to hide something. My preference is to have a clear, transparent CV with the reasons for their unemployment. If the person is of interest to me, then I will definitely do an interview with that person. But I want to know what has happened, I ask questions, and I do not reject someone just because of that. If someone has been fired three times, that is enough for me. But I still want to know the reasons.</p> <p>Being unemployed for more than 1 1/2 years is a problem because their daily life changes and they have a lot of problems to start again. I have seen that these people suffer a lot when they go back to work after such a long period of time. If they have been working in an interim position, that is fine. But if not, it is a question of age, years of work experience. I also check various facts.</p>	<p>It depends on how the gap is argued when applying. Then an interesting person for me is someone who has had further training, such as "I learned about artificial intelligence". If the person has only travelled, then my threshold for an invitation is lower. Nothing against travelling, but I have seen cases where the person has travelled for a month in a 6-month period and then done some training in the last 5 months. Then it is fine.</p> <p>The development in certain areas of the organisation is happening at a fast pace. Even though this person is experienced and would fit, I would doubt that this person would be able to start again fast enough after being out of the system for over a year.</p>	<p>The people who have joined have come from other companies. They do not have a history of unemployment. At least the people in my network, I think that is a fact. They have all come from other companies, from reorganisation, from short periods of unemployment.</p> <p>Women who were unemployed because they had left the labour market for family reasons, children and so on, and then came back because they had done some training, like a master's degree, and then joined our company.</p>

Summary

It seems to be very important how the unemployment period is argued when applying. Unemployment caused by external factors such as the merger or bankruptcy of the company does not matter. Maternity leave, training, interim positions are good explanations and acceptable gaps. Filling the unemployment period exclusively with travelling is not favourable for recruitment. A period of unemployment up to 9 months does not seem to be a critical for recruitment.

5.4.2 Unemployed

Questions:

- How committed are you to your job search?
- What obstacles do you experience when looking for a job?

Unemployed 1	Unemployed 2	Unemployed 3	Unemployed 4
<p>I am very committed. Employers are always looking for the fly in the ointment. They demand that you train and due further education yourself, but when you're paid out, you can't afford it. I can't afford it:</p> <p>I don't have an employer who will pay for further training.</p>	<p>After a long illness, my energy was limited. So, I had to be very focused in my job search. I went to job fairs; I took part in job coaching and I had a couple of people on my side as advisors. Another burden was that the previous organisation I worked for, has a very large network with many closely connected corporate clients. Everybody knew each other and I ran the risk of being excluded from the first selection. They might think, this is the sick person we haven't known about for two years.</p>	<p>I am looking for a job every day, I am doing further education and so on. But I don't have anyone to help me get in touch with the key decision-makers in order to get a job. Without that, I don't think I'm going to get hired.</p>	<p>My search time these days is about four hours a week. LinkedIn is a very good job search platform. Since I started a couple of months ago in my actual 20% job, I want to focus on that and I'm already learning Python, which is a new programming language, on the job. Although I would like to work 60%, I am concentrating on this. My weakness, my difficulty is the German language, my level is good but not enough for the job market.</p>

Summary

Job seekers seem to be highly committed to their search. They visit job fairs, take coaching and work with advisors which seem to be effective channels that are used for job search. The demands of the employers are perceived from the employees as high. They demand further training and education for the job.

The level of German needed for the labour market seems to be difficult to achieve in a country where standard German is almost non-existent in daily life.

5.5 Swiss - Migrants

5.5.1 Line Managers and HR

Questions:

- To what extent is Swiss nationality relevant when hiring a person?

Line Manager 1 - Martin	Human Resources - Susanne	Line Manager 2 - Jafles	Line Manager 3 - Alessandra
<p>Half of the people we employ are not Swiss. Our people are close to Switzerland in terms of culture in Central Europe. A good education and networks are essential, as are languages such as English plus German, French or Italian.</p> <p>The current trend is to hire local staff where we are based. It is more attractive from a financial point of view and much more authentic in terms of know-how and local relationships. When I tell our clients that the strategy to grow in China has been implemented by the Chinese partners and not by me, who knows nothing about China, that is a selling point.</p>	<p>We employ Swiss and Europeans. Europeans because they are allowed to work in Switzerland. That is the reason, nothing else. If a person is from a third country (outside the EU), we usually do not employ them because it is very complicated. You have to advertise for three months and prove why you cannot hire a European or a Swiss for that position.</p>	<p>It is relevant depending on how I want to mix the organisation and it is job-specific. A different mental and cultural attitude is important for diversifying a team. The Swiss are good for positions that require a lot of adaptation and compromise. Other cultural groups are simply quicker and better at negotiating, perhaps because it is part of their daily life. A very harmonious and homogeneous team, in terms of culture or nationality, has some barriers like "no, that's not possible, we won't do that". To bring one or two people from a different culture or nationality into the group that say "why not, let's try it!". Through this different behaviour a certain transformation of the team will be possible.</p>	<p>We are a strong multinational company. Swiss citizens are the minority of our employees. After Covid, we are hiring people from different countries and they don't have to move, they do their work remotely from their countries.</p> <p>Financially, it's very attractive for our company. People and their families don't have to move to Switzerland. The costs of relocation are very high for the company and not always successful for the family.</p>

Summary

A cultural mix in the organisation and a job-related profile seem to be key criteria for recruiting Swiss and European people. Europeans are allowed to work in Switzerland but people from third countries (non-EU) experience major bureaucratic obstacles to being hired. The current trend is to have local staff in the various countries where the company has a presence. It is financially very attractive; Employees on the ground in the respective country have better knowledge, relationships and networks that are very useful for the company than external ones.

5.5.2 Unemployed

Questions:

- Does your nationality play a role in the job search?

Unemployed 1	Unemployed 2	Unemployed 3	Unemployed 4
It's not relevant.	They are looking for the right person for the job in the international, global private sector, such as export or other markets. I'm a secondo, I grew up in Switzerland and I introduce myself in Swiss German. That's an advantage.	Nationality plays a big part in this. People tell me that my German isn't 100 per cent good, and that's a problem. In international companies I have a chance to work, but in Swiss national companies I do not. German and Swiss German are very relevant for the job, they want these languages at mother tongue level.	In Zurich they would give me the opportunity for interviews as long as I have a work permit. I have the feeling that nationality is not an issue.

Summary

The international companies tend to be open to all nationalities if people bring the necessary skills. Medium-sized national companies tend to require a good knowledge of the German language and nationals.

5.6 Age

5.6.1 Line Managers and HR

Questions:

- Are people aged 50+ being recruited?

Line Manager 1 - Martin	Human Resources - Susanne	Line Manager 2 - Jafles	Line Manager 2 - Alessandra
Age can be an advantage if the person brings with them extremely good experience. So, if someone has been CEO of a company 2-3 times, has changed and is looking for a job at the age of 50, for example, but brings that experience. This means that we are buying 20 to 30 years of experience from that person. That is probably one percent of the workforce.	In my career, I have recruited a lot of people over 50. If someone is over 58, the question of pensioning starts to arise, but if that person's intention is to work until the retirement, that is fine. Having the right skills and experience is more important than age. We need to make sure we have a good age mix on our team. I do not see age on the curriculum vitae.	Certain ages are better suited to a job than others. Young people in entry-level positions are eager to take the next step in their careers and are more willing to put in extra hours than their older counterparts. "If I need the experience described in the job ad, it doesn't matter to me if this person started at 20 and already has 10 or 15 years of experience in the field, or started at 40 and is now 55. I want the years of experience".	Yes, in most cases former employees have come back from other companies. They have a background and knowledge of our company, which makes everything easier, from onboarding to everything else. It does happen, but it does not seem to happen very often. The experience they bring with them is very important.

Summary

The importance of having the right skills and experience was mentioned as being more important than age. Age could be an advantage if the person brings with them a very good level of experience of between 10 and 30 years. Former employees who come back to the company and who have a lot of experience seem to be very welcome.

5.6.2 Unemployed

Questions:

- Does your age play a role in the job search?

Unemployed 1	Unemployed 2	Unemployed 3	Unemployed 4
I am told: "You will retire in two years; don't you want to take early retirement?" I say: "No, I like working." They tell me "We want someone who can stay longer with us." I would like to work longer; I find it exciting and interesting and I can also contribute a lot because I have a lot of experience. I am not old-fashioned anyway; I am young at heart.	I began to look for categories of possible super industries or jobs. That then helped me to look more specifically and that is where my profile fits. But in a typical industrial job at the age of 40, as a generalist, I realised I had no chance.	Maybe my age also is an issue. I think this is also because I have been in a job interview at UBS. When I told them I am 50 they said: "Oh, I am so sorry. I am looking for someone younger."	So far it does not affect me. I think if you are over 35 or older, employers think you do not adapt easily to changes. The industry is always changing and new technologies are coming now. So, they want someone who is adapting quickly to changes.

Summary

The perception of some unemployed people in the face-to-face interviews gave the impression that it is already more difficult to find a job from the age of 35-40, as younger people are preferred because they are considered more adaptable and flexible. For those close to retirement age, the time horizon they need to work is also seen as a negative factor.

5.7 Person-Job-Fit

5.7.1 Line Managers and HR

Questions:

- To what extent is the Person-Job-Fit relevant for recruitment?

Line Manager 1 - Martin	Human Resources - Susanne	Line Manager 2 - Jafles	Line Manager 3 - Alessandra
<p>There are certain criteria that employees must meet: Master's degree, 5 average, to have a Swiss cultural relation. A background in business administration or strategy is an advantage.</p> <p>These are the criteria. There are 2 - 3 must-haves, where we must have a 100% fit, and there are 2 - 3 criteria where the person must have a 60-70% fit to be shortlisted. So far, we have been able to sort things out in this way. In 10 years', time, with the "war for talents", we will probably have to adjust our criteria slightly.</p>	<p>At the start of the recruitment process, I have a briefing with the manager to establish their needs for the position. There are must-haves and nice-to-have. Among other skills needed for the position, motivation is important.</p>	<p>There are certain aspects that are must criteria for hiring. There are always some of these 3 requirements in the job description that must be there.</p> <p>The person's application may not be a 100% match, but there is a certain attitude that I experience from the person in the interview, where I think that although this person, who does not have 5 years of experience, but only 3, has convinced me that he or she is able to compensate for this gap through his or her attitude.</p>	<p>Mobility, flexibility, and extensive travel will be a requirement. Skills and competencies in addition to language and knowledge are important. Working conditions like income, our company is well</p> <p>above the market, it is more in terms of work-life balance.</p> <p>When you are young, everyone likes to travel around the world. But maybe there is a time in your life when you are less available for that. This is where we as a company need to improve.</p>

Summary

From the responses of the line managers and HR, it can be summarised that the Person-Job-Fit is very important for being hired. There are some must-have criteria for the job and others that can be negotiated in the recruitment interview.

5.7.2 Unemployed

Questions:

- To what extent does your profile match the requirements of the labour market?

Unemployed 1	Unemployed 2	Unemployed 3	Unemployed 4
I am an executive assistant. Yes, my education and experience are in demand on the labour market. About 70% of my skills match the advertised jobs. I also try to stay up to date with the latest tools and techniques.	I have a typical generalist profile. The longer the more it becomes a handicap for you. A job could be at the level of the confederation, cantons, work, maybe associations or companies with an international impact. But in a typical industrial job at the age of 40, as a generalist, I realised I had no chance.	I think my profile mainly matches like 70% and I have 25 years of experience. It matches very well, but when it comes to the language, my German skills are too poor. I can do everything and now I have taken courses to improve my computer knowledge and German.	I am a Junior but the market is always searching for senior developers. They want someone who knows everything instead of training someone.

Summary

The answers from the face-to-face interviews show that the person-job fit is an indispensable component for finding a job. However, in some cases a good person-job fit is not enough, for example when the age of the person comes into play.

5.8 Sustainable Employment

5.8.1 Line Managers and HR

Questions:

- Which factors are relevant for sustainable employment?
- To what extent is the Person-Organisation-Fit (P-O-Fit) relevant in sustainable employment?

Line Manager 1 - Martin	Human Resources - Susanne	Line Manager 2 - Jafles	Line Manager 3 - Alessandra
<p>We expect employees to develop regularly and if we can see a development, they can stay and are promoted. We recommend that, until the partner level which is maybe in 15 years.</p> <p>Person-Organisation-Fit becomes a criterion from manager onwards. Up to manager level it is content, skills and capabilities. From the manager level onwards, the leadership skills come into it and that is where the person-organisation fit comes in. If they have the same purpose as we had, if they stand behind the organisation, they can develop the organisation further and that is where it will become increasingly important. And when you become a partner, practically the top level, then part of the selection criteria is "What has this person done for the team, for the organisation, etc.?", "Is he capable of developing the team?"</p>	<p>Persons need to be very flexible and must embrace change. Because we are a very dynamic company and you need to cope with this, otherwise this is the wrong company for you.</p> <p>You need to work together with people in global teams. We are so international; they need to love an international environment.</p>	<p>Social competence is very important. You always must be able to interact with others and work in teams. From the moment this top-qualified person does not have this social competence, then I would say that is a sustainability issue for me. Then this person is no longer operational for me, no longer to be seen as a resource, but rather as a burden.</p>	<p>I think, the working conditions are key because if a person does not feel OK in his work environment, then this will not last for long. When it comes to income, employment conditions, I think in our company we are in any case well above a certain level on the market and so that is not an issue, it is more in terms of working conditions and work life balance. This goes back to the personal commitment in the job, in the trips, because of course managing work life balance with that can be challenging for an extended time.</p>

Summary

According to the responses of line managers and HR, the Person-Organisation Fit and sustainability of the job depends strongly on the requirements that an organisation or company has and what an employee is willing to do over a longer period of time. The requirements vary considerably from one organisation or company to another.

5.8.2 Unemployed

Questions:

- How is the quality of the job offers for you in relation to your requirements (permanent/temporary position, full-time/part-time, income, etc.)?

Unemployed 1	Unemployed 2	Unemployed 3	Unemployed 4
<p>I look at both temporary and permanent positions. The permanent positions are mostly between 80% and 100%, while the temporary positions are mostly 100%. Once in a while there is something with 60%. I need this 80% for subsistence, the income of a 60% position is not enough.</p>	<p>The economy is looking for talent, as I said, more and more specific profiles, despite a very uncertain environment. The jobs are almost always permanent compared to the rest of Europe. That is the beauty of Switzerland, people are looking for people, it is a partnership of equals, employer - employee.</p> <p>Companies are trying to position themselves with offers like work-life balance, goodies, and benefits for employees. You can see that employers also have to position themselves to have the bright minds.</p> <p>I noticed a gap between better paid jobs in the private sector with less purpose, less exciting and tending to be more in Zurich versus other areas such as startups, foundations, cooperatives, NGOs where there were wonderful purposes coupled with my values.</p> <p>Then you get into a conversation and you realise that I would have had to give up a third to half or more of my last salary. And that was the big challenge for me, to combine both.</p>	<p>In my experience, you get to a point where you do not matter if it is permanent. If you are getting 70%, even 30%, you are ok. I am willing to work. I do not care if it is half time or if they are giving me a contract just for one year. For me it is not important</p>	<p>In Zurich are good conditions, are very good prices. They give you a part-time job if you are working many years. Otherwise, they do not want to hire new employees part time. They always want someone who works 100%. I think they should give the opportunity to work less.</p> <p>Schools are half days; they are not full days. If you send your kids every day to the Kita's (child day care centres). I do not think that is also good. They prefer to hire someone who only works, without considering work life balance.</p>

Summary

From the answers given, it can be seen that the characteristics of quality in work can vary greatly depending on the sector and on the employer concerned.

6 Discussion

The results of the present study provide no clear conclusions regarding the stated hypotheses: Successful former unemployed have lower values on some barriers, higher values on few facilitators, they are a socio-demographically different group and there are no job-related variables that make a difference.

6.1 Hypothesis 1

The best predictors differentiating between successful and unsuccessful unemployed people in the case of facilitators were career adaptability control and self-regulation goal. Controlling for all other possible predictors these two variables, however, were not significant in the multivariate logistic regression, instead career adaptability concern was significant. This shows together with the higher level of anxiety that it is important that people take the unemployment serious, considering the negative consequences if one is not getting a job.

Curiosity and control were mentioned as highly desirable in the face-to-face interviews and therefore, could be important indicators for an efficient and successful career. In addition, confidence in one's own possibilities and abilities was stated as a very important prerequisite to advance professionally.

Commitment to development in different environments of the company and willingness to internal and external training were mentioned as a must and adaptability as a key factor for good performance.

Contrary to existing research of an association of low self-esteem and unemployment (Alvaro et al., 2019; Paul & Moser, 2009) self-esteem had no influence on employment status in our study.

Unemployed people know less people of importance and have less social support. Various studies showed that unemployed people have less social support (Roberts et al., 1997, Lampert & Kroll, 2011) and smaller social networks (Diewald, 2007; Gallie et al., 2001). Rozer et al., (2020) show that the effects of unemployment differ between different social categories. Older individuals lose social contact after both short- and long-term unemployment: network size, contact frequency (not if they remain unemployed), and network support decline. The effects of unemployment are more negative (or in case of long-term unemployment less positive) for network support, than for network size and contact frequency. The changes in the network differ also between types of social relationship. Weaker ties (neighbours and acquaintances) seem more affected than stronger ties (family and friends). Support (but not size) of acquaintance relations declines for each social category after short- and long-term unemployment. Unemployment decreases public but increases private social activities. There were no differences between reasons for unemployment based on social norms and labour market prospects (Kunze & Suppa, 2017). Social networks foster the chances of finding a job in unemployed people (Krug, Trappmann, & Wolf 2020).

In the present study, the unemployed mentioned in the face-to-face interviews the importance of social networks such as LinkedIn as common for job searches. Job fairs, meet-ups - online or face-to-face - are also considered helpful. Getting to know people personally, mentors, multipliers, gate openers are said to be a big advantage in getting an inside of the companies and getting recommended by them. That has been stated to be a great help.

The face-to-face interviews it was stated that the use of employee networks as a recruitment channel has become very important and that some companies were struggling to fill vacancies without finding suitable candidates, especially in sectors such as IT, etc. It was mentioned that the social bond would imply a certain responsibility and the risk for the company would be lower. Employees would only recommend a good colleague, and the candidate would feel socially obliged to the colleague who referred them. Employees would receive a bonus if they recommended someone and the person was hired.

Networks seem to be a considerable help for finding a job which is also reflected in the present study by the response given to the question "What are the reasons you found a job?" in the second survey. About 16% of the unemployed from PES which participated in the second survey gave «networks» as one of the reasons for finding a job (see table 3).

Career adaptability involves proactively planning one's career and extending one's competences and skills.

In the present study, curiosity and control were mentioned as highly desirable in the face-to-face interviews and therefore, could be important indicators for an efficient and successful career. In addition, confidence in one's own possibilities and abilities was stated as a very important prerequisite to advance professionally. Commitment to development in different environments of the company and willingness to internal and external training were mentioned as a must and adaptability as a key factor for good performance.

Career adaptability and self-regulation showed significant associations with t2 employment status in the model with only facilitators, but not in the model with all variables, showing that these concepts are related to other predictors of finding employment.

Career Adaptability is an important factor in unemployment for finding a job. In unemployed people career decision making and career confidence positively predicted reemployment quality 8 months later (Koen et al., 2010). Students with higher levels of concern, control, curiosity, and confidence are more likely to be employed 18 months after the labour market transition (Monteiro et al., 2019). Career adaptability can contribute to the prospects of unemployment, as Klehe et al., (2011) demonstrate that in an organisational downsizing those with high career adaptability in form of career exploration had higher job-search behaviours and turnover. The importance of optimism was evaluated in a study of workers pursuing business courses: developmental leadership and career optimism relate positively to career adaptability, but only for employees low on optimism (Delle & Searle, 2022). It is important for unemployed people to stay optimistic and optimistically and actively pursue their career after the unemployment. This is confirmed via the study by Gander, Hofmann & Ruch (2021): Gaining employment went along with increases in the orientations to pleasure, engagement, and meaning while a decrease in the orientation to pleasure was observed in the constantly unemployed. Getting a job led to increases in life satisfaction, decreases in mental health problems, and increases in all orientations to happiness. Also stressing the

importance of career adaptability people in the present study named further education as the third important reason for finding the job.

Self-regulation is important for employees to keep the job (Porath, C. L., Bateman, T. S., 2006) and for the unemployed to get a job (Liu, S., et al., 2014). As self-regulation is impaired after social exclusion and unemployed are often socially excluded, we expect lesser self-regulation regulation in the unemployed than the employed (Baumeister et al., 2005). If self-regulation is low, the probability of unemployment rises, as the study of Daly et al., (2015) reports: From labour-market entry to middle age, individuals with low self-control experienced 1.6 times as many months of unemployment as those with high self-control. In another study (Creed et al., 2009) learning goal orientation and self-regulation predicted job-seeking intensity, self-regulation mediated between learning goal orientation and job-seeking intensity. Job-seeking intensity however did not mediate the relationship between human capital, goal orientation, and self-regulation variables with reemployment outcomes. That goal-setting was as in our study significant higher in unemployed people can be because their most important goal is to get a job.

6.2 Hypothesis 2

Concerning barriers such as procrastination, anxiety, physical health, loneliness, and psychic health were significant predictors of finding employment. The negative effect of loneliness is in line with positive effects of social networks and social support, which are often lost, when one gets unemployed. Morrish et al., (2022) suggest bidirectionality in the relationship: Experience of loneliness in at least one of their ten survey waves increased the probability of being unemployed in the last wave by 17.5%. These longitudinal results indicate a larger impact of loneliness on unemployment than the reverse. Lonelier young adults were less confident in their employment prospects, had a reduced job search motivation and were more likely to be out of work, probably because of a lower workplace performance (Matthews et al., 2019). Even for employed people loneliness was predictive of future work disability onset when adjusting for other factors in the disablement process (Morris, 2020). In a meta-analysis Morrish and Medina-Lara (2021) observed a positive association between unemployment and loneliness across all studies, revealing an at least 40% increase in the likelihood of reporting loneliness when unemployed. The magnitude of this relationship increases with the severity of loneliness and appears to peak at age 30-34 and 50-59. Furthermore, the authors confirm the bidirectionality of the relationship between loneliness and unemployment.

In the present study, the face-to-face interviews suggested that there is a need for both employees and employers to be involved in health management. Nowadays we are dealing with a very stressful work environment and employees must work under a lot of pressure. Therefore, more action needs to be taken to improve health in companies. Support from friends and the community is needed in difficult situations. Loneliness needs to be recognized and people around the concerned person need to take action.

The present study indicates that worse physical and mental health is associated with a higher risk of remaining unemployed. Previous research has shown that unemployed people were more vulnerable to adverse health (Drydakis, 2015; Ferry et al., 2021; Gander et al., 2021; Minelli et al., 2014). It is well established that unemployed people have worse health

than employed people (Roberts et al., 1997; Isaksson et al., 2004; Kroll & Lambert 2011; Kroll et al., 2016; von der Lippe & Rattay, 2016). Both psychic and physical health were impaired in unemployed people and this result isn't dependant on age. The sample of the present study is comparable to the mean age of Swiss people 42.64³. Bad physical and mental health in unemployed people may be explained by low levels of social support (s. Milner et al., 2016). Krug and Prechsl (2020) consider social integration as crucially important for understanding the adverse effect of unemployment on mental health. In the causal path hypothesis, social integration has a positive effect on the health of the unemployed. According to the buffering hypothesis social integration shields the unemployed from negative health effects. Gebel & Voßemer (2014) report that bad health leads to losing a job and a better health increases the probability for getting a job. The research of Lee et al., (2019) show that unemployment can have long-term health effects: The duration of unemployment across young adulthood increased mental health problems at age 39, regardless of gender. An important finding of the study of Li et al., (2023) is that unemployed individuals were about 30% more likely to use health services compared to those employed, mainly mental health services. Mental health problems were reported to be driven by financial pressure, social network, disposable time and depression/anxiety. All these researches including the results of the present study show, that it is important to look after ones' physical and mental health when unemployed.

There is much evidence that loneliness is a high-risk factor for physical health, mental health and mortality (Holt-Lundtstad et al., 2015; Rico-Urbe et al., 2018; Paul, Bu & Fancourt, 2021). Therefore, it is highly important for unemployed people to reduce loneliness in order to improve health. Establishing social networks for the unemployed leads to less loneliness and better health. This must be recognized and addressed directly at the beginning of unemployment.

On the basis of the face-to-face interview responses, physical disabilities do not seem to be an obstacle to be employed, but in the quantitative results (see table 12: Results of the multiple logistic regression for both samples) of the present study, poor health was a significant negative factor in finding a job.

A surprising effect found in the present study was that procrastination had a positive effect on getting a job. This is contrary to previous research findings showing that high levels of procrastination are associated with lower salaries, shorter durations of employment, and a greater likelihood of being unemployed or underemployed rather than working full-time (Nyugen, Steel & Ferrari, 2013). Van Hooft, Wanberg, & Van Hoyer (2013) and Horvath (2022) replicate this finding of negative effects of procrastination on job search.

³ <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/216782/umfrage/durchschnittsalter-der-bevoelkerung-in-der-schweiz/#:~:text=Durchschnittsalter%20der%20Bev%C3%B6lkerung%20in%20der%20Schweiz%20bis%202019.,Schweiz%20einen%20neuen%20H%C3%B6chststand%20von%20rund%2042%2C64%20Jahren.>

Examining the argument whether perceived social exclusion during unemployment leads to procrastination through online media, which in turn lessens the job search efforts of the unemployed. Müller et al., (2018) found that online procrastination plays an important role in the lives of the unemployed but has no immediate effects on their perceived job search efforts. More important for job search efforts is the amount of motivational control that the unemployed can muster. Thus, the recreational use of online media as such is not necessarily detrimental to the efforts invested in finding a job; instead, online skill-building and motivational support are key antecedents to better empower the unemployed to use the internet productively for finding reemployment.

In the present study change from employment to unemployment and change from employment to another status as well as another status to employment had the highest means in procrastination at t1. There were no differences between the three unemployed groups (finding a job. vs. not finding a job vs. change to another work status) and also no overall difference between t2 and t1 in procrastination. Findings of Przepiorka, Blachnio & Cudo (2023) may explain the present unexpected results regarding procrastination. They showed that those students who procrastinated often, reported a high tendency to engage in problematic new media use and a high level of future anxiety. If job seekers have the strategy of performance-avoid goal orientation (PAGO) they tend to show avoidance-oriented responses such as procrastination and anxiety during the pursuit of employment goals (Kanar, 2017). Affum-Osei and Chan (2023) replicate this result: PAGO job seekers searched more haphazardly and their search behaviour was less focused and exploratory. Tibbett & Ferrari (2019) report that indecision and regrets about education, career, and finances increased the likelihood of identifying as a procrastinator. If someone is unemployed regrets about the absolved education and former career are very likely.

Also surprising was that in the present study anxiety had a positive influence on finding a job. This indicates that it is helpful to be concerned if somebody is unemployed and should be aware of future consequences. If an unemployed person has existential anxiety, they may be more motivated to do something about it. Nevertheless, research shows that unemployed people with high anxiety and depression scores develop maladaptive coping strategies such as substance use, self-blaming, self-distraction or denial (Navarro-Abal et al., 2018). However, in the present study, the effects of anxiety were controlled for mental (and physical) health leading to the conclusion, that the non-clinical aspects of anxiety are helpful for finding employment. The results of Wang et al., (2017) show that cognitive reappraisal is positively related to job search behaviour, while expressive suppression is negatively related to job search behaviour. Anxiety was negatively related to job search behaviour (and cognitive reappraisal), while job search self-efficacy was positively associated with job search behaviour. The study of Kim et al., (2022) found that job-seeking anxiety showed a high level of job preparation behaviour. The anxiety levels in our sample were rather low, and the scale we used asks about nervousness, being on edge, not being able to stop or control worrying. Indirect support for a positive relationship between anxiety and finding a job is also provided by the study of Stevenor and Zickar (2022): Job search behaviour correlates positively with job insecurity but also with number of job interviews, number of jobs offers and turnover intentions. Further, job search behaviour was strongly positively correlated, yet not redundant, with job search effort.

The unemployment history was not a significant predictor of finding a job in the quantitative analysis of the present study. Nevertheless, in the face-to-face interviews of the present study, the line managers and HR stated that for them it is very important how the unemployment period is argued when applying. Unemployment caused by external factors such as the merger or bankruptcy of the company does not matter. Maternity leave, training, interim positions are good explanations and acceptable gaps. Filling the unemployment period exclusively with travelling is not favourable for recruitment. A period of unemployment up to 9 months does not seem to be a critical for recruitment.

6.3 Hypothesis 3

All four sociodemographic variables reached significance in the model, in which they were the only predictors. But in the model with all predictors only age and sex remained significant. Education level and migrant status had no significant influence when controlled for all other variables. Only 35.9% of the unemployed men changed to employment, but 41.0% of the women. However, 77.5% of the men, who found employment, got a full-time job and only 55.7% of the formerly unemployed women. If unemployed women get a job, it will often be a part-time job, as part-time work is generally more common in women⁴.

According to the answers from the face-to-face interviews in the present study a cultural mix in the organisation and a job-related profile seem to be a key criterium for recruiting Swiss as well as European people. Europeans are allowed to work in Switzerland but people from third countries (non-EU) experience major bureaucratic obstacles to being hired. The current trend is to have local staff in the various countries where the company has a presence. It is financially very attractive; Employees on the ground in the respective country have better knowledge, relationships and networks that are very useful for the company than external ones. These outcomes are consistent with the results from the quantitative analysis of this study, in which Swiss nationality had no significant influence on finding a job.

The differences between people with or without Swiss nationality were moderate: 71.5% Swiss, 67.6% Non-Swiss previously unemployed encountered employment. People who have a migrant background or belong to an ethnic minority have a higher probability to be unemployed (Drinkwater, 2017; Pedulla, 2018), longer periods of unemployment, shorter periods of employment and a longer job search (Drinkwater, 2017; Uhlenborff & Zimmermann, 2014). Differences may partly depend on differences in education (Cebolla-Boado et al., 2015). All these studies on migrants emphasize that they are not a homogenous group, instead there are big differences between migrant groups with some having even lower unemployment rates than natives, as in the United States, Israel (Drinkwater, 2017) and in Ireland people from the European Community (McGinnity et al., 2020). Auer et al., (2019) conducted a survey in Switzerland. They found that employers' evaluations of non-natives follow sociocultural distance perceptions and that a non-native background is a disadvantage mainly in high-skilled occupations, whereas in low-skilled

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/w/EDN-20230303-1>

occupations, having a migrant background is less detrimental. In May 2023 Swiss people had an unemployment rate of 1.3%, the non-Swiss living in Switzerland of 3.5% (SECO, 2023).

In quantitative analysis of the present study, age is a significant negative predictor of employment. The face-to-face interviews with the unemployed underlined that result. They gave the impression that it is already more difficult to find a job from the age of 35-40, as younger people are preferred because they are considered more adaptable and flexible. For people who are close to retirement age, the employment time horizon also plays a negative role. According to the line managers age could be an advantage if the person brings with them a very good level of experience of between 10 and 30 years.

For older unemployed people it is very hard to find a job. If one loses a job over the age of 50 the chances of re-employment are rather low. This was confirmed in a lot of studies (Axelrad et al., 2018; Stier & Endevelde, 2015; Thomassen et al., 2020). The present sample was rather young on the average and the unemployed people probably therefore had a lower mean age than in the general Swiss population. The Swiss unemployment rates for the age groups of 25-49 and 50-64 are with 1.7% and 1.9% comparable (Seco, 2023) and there is no interaction with gender effects.

In the present study, only unemployed people who had no education at all were less likely to find a job and those with a university degree. Results from the literature indicate that education significantly increases re-employment rates of the unemployed. (Riddell & Song, 2011). Therefore, it is an important point for unemployed people to engage in further education. Lavrinovicha et al., (2015) show for Latvia, the U.S. Bureau of labor Statistics⁵ for the USA, or the PES Network of the EU⁶ that the risk of unemployment diminishes with increasing educational attainment while this is not the case in the present sample.

6.4 Hypothesis 4

The job-related variables P-O-Fit, P-J-Fit, Job Commitment and Job Passion could not predict success in finding employment. This was different to the results of the initial baseline study, which compared unemployed people with employed people. In the present study, the unemployed people were asked at t1 about the last job. On the one hand, there can be memory effects or resentiments. On the other hand, job-related variables regarding the last job may not be relevant for finding a job in the future.

In the present study, line managers and HR mention in the face-to-face interviews that the person-job fit is a necessary requirement for finding a job. However, in some cases a good person-job fit is not enough, for example when the age of the person comes into play. According to the responses of the line managers and HR, it can be summarised that the Person-Job-Fit is very important for being hired. There are some must-have criteria for the job and others that can be negotiated in the recruitment interview.

⁵ <https://www.bls.gov/emp/chart-unemployment-earnings-education.htm>

⁶ <https://www.pesnetwork.eu/2019/09/05/lmb3-educational-attainment/>

Job passion is not much studied in unemployed people. Scales and Brown (2020) report associations of job passion and job commitment with voluntary turnover. In the initial baseline study, there was a difference in job passion between employed and unemployed people. However, according to the present results, job passion shown in the previous job does not predict the success in finding a new job.

According to the statements of line managers and HR in the face-to-face interviews of the current study, the Person-Organisation-Fit and sustainability of the job depends strongly on the requirements that an organisation or company has and what an employee is willing to do over a longer period of time. The requirements vary considerably from one organisation or company to another.

According to our knowledge, there are no studies on the relationship between P-O-Fit and unemployment. Indirect inferences can be drawn based on studies that investigate the influence of P-O-Fit on turnover and dismissal. P-O-Fit was found to be a strong predictor of work engagement and work engagement is negatively related to employees' turnover intention. Further, work engagement mediated the relationship between P-O-Fit and turnover intention. Boon and Biron (2016) found that higher needs–supplies fit at T2 are associated with lower turnover at T3. In contrast, among employees in high-quality leader–member exchange relationships, the demands–abilities dimension of Person–Job-Fit at T2 is associated with higher turnover at T3. Sylva et al., (2019) found in their two-wave study comparing individuals who had switched jobs between wave 1 and wave 2 to those who had not, that turnover was i) preceded by lower levels of the perceived demands-abilities fit; ii) accompanied by an increase in the level of career initiative; and iii) associated with greater improvement in perceived demands-abilities fit.

6.5 Hypothesis 5

The present study is based on two different samples: One with self-declared unemployed and employed (sample 2) and the other one with unemployed officially registered at PES of a Swiss canton (sample 3).

In sample 2 education, gender, career adaptability control, age, loneliness, anxiety, and psychic health were significant predictors of getting a job.

In sample 3 only three indicators reached significance when controlling for all other predictors: Procrastination, Career adaptability concern, and psychic health.

In the analysis with both samples combined age, anxiety, gender, loneliness, psychic health, physical health, career adaptability concern and procrastination were significant predictors of formerly unemployed to find a job. This shows that high career adaptability, a good health, a low level of loneliness as well as anxiety and procrastination when keeping health constant are helpful for finding a job.

6.6 Hypothesis 6

The overall aim for the job-seeker is the establishment of a sustainable employment. Therefore, it is important to test, if there are any differences between those who are employed since a long time and those who only recently found a job.

The present results show that the newly employed have significantly lower levels in all dark triad scales and all job-related scales, but higher levels in career adaptability, social support

and self-esteem than the long-term employed. In self-regulation perseverance they have higher levels but in self-regulation goalsetting their values are lower. There are no differences in physical and psychic health as well as in social capital scales between the newly and long-term employed. Higher levels of self-esteem in newly employed may be explained via an increase in self-esteem right after finding a job. The fact that anxiety is still higher among newly hired workers can possibly be explained by the greater uncertainty regarding expectations of skills and the environment in the new workplace. Several studies report the important effect of job anxiety, depending on job insecurity, job demands and harassment on mental health (Aygapong et al., 2022; Vignoli et al., 2017; Muschalla & Linden, 2007; Zhang et al., 2023).

Personality traits associated with the dark triad show up strongest in interaction with other people. Such interactions are reduced in the unemployed. Kaufman, Wheeler and Soho (2021) showed connections of the dark triad scales with job commitment. For individuals who have worked in part-time/casual employment for longer, Machiavellianism and psychopathy have significantly stronger negative associations with affective commitment. In contrast, among individuals who have had a significant career interruption, Machiavellianism had a significantly stronger positive association with continuance commitment. However, on the long run people high in the dark triad traits can lead to disastrous consequences for an organization (Schiemann & Jonas, 2020). People with dark triad traits are more often found in leadership positions (Diller et al., 2021).

Breaching and burnout often lead to a turnover, therefore they should be prevented. One should be aware that former unemployed people are more vulnerable because of their previous unemployment. It should therefore be avoided that an unemployed person is hired and then made redundant after a short period of time. Therefore, it is advisable to make sure that there is an adequate person-job and person-organisation fit upon re-employment, so that sustainable employment can be achieved.

7 Limitations

One limitation of the present study can be found in the measurement of employment status in sample 2 because it was a self-report. We also do not know whether the unemployed in sample 2 were registered with the PES. In addition, it would have been helpful if we had information on duration of unemployment for the unemployed and employment of the employed.

Because of time restrictions in conducting the online survey, only a limited number of variables could be measured. The dropout rate from time point 1 to time point 2 was considerable.

8 Conclusion

The present study's main goal was the assessment of the factors relevant for sustainable employment in both unemployed and employed people. A special focus is on the comparison between those previously unemployed people who found employment versus those who did not.

In addition to the facilitators such as Career Adaptability, the barriers such as loneliness, bad psychic and physical health as negative factors, and anxiety as a positive one must also be considered. Loneliness and health are both factors that the PES should consider when offering courses in health management. Based on the present results, it is also important to promote career planning.

Our findings support the need for a paradigm shift in Swiss PES when it comes to designing interventions to alleviate unemployment and in particular to work with the long-term unemployed. They should focus on effective measures to meet the needs of the unemployed, such as investing in appropriate further education, skills, and competences to close the portfolio gap, soft skills training to boost confidence as well as their networking skills to connect them with decision-makers and key players who can enable them to enter the labour market.

It is time to push for institutional change that maximises people's resources and includes them in the working process. In addition, it is important for PES to intensify networking with employers and make it efficient so that they can effectively bridge the gap with the economy. This is particularly urgent for the long-term unemployed, so that unemployment does not mark the end of the work life for them.

Furthermore, the present results suggest, that employers should focus more on the workload and work-life balance of the employees in order to prevent burnout as well as mental and physical diseases. Considering the negative effects of health problems on the probability of finding employment, they should increasingly pay attention to people with physical or psychological disabilities when recruiting. Measures also need to be taken regarding loneliness. Other countries and organisations (WHO, CDC) have already established programmes and even ministries (Japan, UK) to alleviate loneliness.

The design of active labour market policies (ALMP) needs reflection on long-term unemployment. Our findings show that with regard to age (50+), physical and mental disabilities, labour market policies are needed to avoid discrimination in these areas and thereby foster health and the chances of sustainable employment.

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